

Abstract

Future can be predicted with great certainty when it has already happened elsewhere. In example, events in embryonic development of a human being can very accurately be predicted due to great relative equality in development between individuals of species.

Many (or all) cells and events in development (evolution) are preceded by precursor cells and events.

I have hypothesized elsewhere that evolution of complex life on the surface of Earth during Phanerozoic is part of Earth's neurogenesis and that this process is qualitatively similar to neurogenesis of standard scale complex life.

Major extinction events here mark the events of cell/protein migration to mantle layers. Since major extinction event is currently happening on Earth, a lot of upcoming events can be predicted based on comparison with past such events and standard scale neurogenesis.

Predictable (expected) events should thus be asteroid bombardments, earthquakes, volcanism, floods, etc. While all of these events should be global (or have a global effect), each of these should be preceded by smaller scale [precursor] events.

If precursor phenomena are concentrated in localized space/time, then these could be considered *root* events, occurring in a general precursor frame. Since cells and proteins also exist as precursors, a general precursor frame should be associated with a general precursor cell and/or a protein.

Such protein should be more evolved than most other proteins of the same species at the time. In context of Earth development, one species of precursor neural proteins should be human beings. Here, I hypothesize that I am one of the general precursors. If that is the case, a lot of my experiences should be precursors to global experiences. Here, many of the experiences I believe are such precursors are presented and discussed.

Journey through future: Evidence of general precursor events

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January 6, 2025

1 Definitions

1.1 General precursor

A general precursor is an individual of population whose current space/time is generally entangled (correlated) with future space/time of general population. This correlation is aligned.

Like any entanglement it is not absolutely lossless. Here, correlated phenomena include physical and mental lifestyle, living conditions and, thus, experiences that impact these conditions and states, but more specific details will not be preserved - e.g., reason for particular experience or condition will generally be different.

Due to difference in karma, not only reasons for change of states may be different, but magnitude of impact.

Current space/time of a general precursor may also be correlated with current space/time of general population, however, such correlation is generally anti-aligned (e.g., lifestyle of general population may be a complete opposite to the lifestyle of a general precursor). I hypothesize that this changes with a *pulse* of strong evolution, when evolution of general population accelerates while evolution of a general precursor decelerates, leading to relative synchronization.

The exact reason for apparent relativity in causes but lack of relativity in effects is likely in lossy compression of evolution - favouring (preserving) effects while the cause is [naturally] selected, favouring a solution most efficient on a particular scale.

1.1.1 Relativity in general precursors

As relativity exists in everything, there's relativity in general precursors and general precursor events. One may then ask the following:

- what percentage of population or what kind of population will be experiencing these events,
- is it limited to individuals of specific sex (male/female),
- is it limited to specific subspecies of individuals (polarized/neutral),
- etc.

From my experience, sex (male/female) or polarization is generally irrelevant, although, I have noticed some phenomena I have experienced during the last days of my polarized nature are now being experienced mostly by women.

This could signal that women are generally core neutral, they are only temporarily expressing polarized behaviour and will eventually experience soul transformation (as I did) when this polarization will recede.

I believe, however, that most phenomena described here are gender/sex/polarization invariant and will be experienced by most of population eventually.

In any case, this should not be some far future, the phenomena should be occurring globally within the coming decades. Some are already becoming global.

Also, at some point, divergence must occur (even if temporary) and future of population will split into at least two pathways (general precursor stops being general precursor).

I believe polarized population will relatively regress (decreasing consciousness/intelligence) into hybrids (some temporarily) while neutral population will stagnate but may later continue progressive or even regressive evolution (in some individuals).

Causality is relative. Therefore, an equivalent global event can precede, or be synchronized with, the precursor event and this becomes more likely with the advancement of strong evolution.

2 Introduction

I hypothesize that I am a general precursor. Thus, many events concentrated around me and in me, impacting my life, are precursors to such events on global scale. Here I will present some phenomena that either already are, or I believe will become, evidence of these precursor events.

Evidence for hypothesized [precursors of] strong (accelerated) evolution will also be presented.

A neutral general precursor is likely to be experiencing synchronicity events on a regular basis.

A belief of a neutral general precursor has significant probability to represent a precursor to general knowledge.

Note also that precursors to a global phenomenon can manifest on the level of individuals, communities and countries, although country precursor may generally be preceded by a community precursor, which may generally be preceded by an individual precursor.

Perhaps most of these events will be seen as undesirable or catastrophic, however, due to lower intensity and magnitude, at least some of the precursor events may even be beneficial for the habitat and life of a general precursor rather than destructive. In example, global intensive flooding (which is likely to be interpreted as a catastrophic or cataclysmic event from polarized human perspective) should have a precursor in a localized event (or events) of lower intensity. This may involve rains or emergence of natural springs, in either case it is more likely to be seen as positive in the coming future, especially after drought or if experienced on higher grounds.

Based on my theories, research and experience, I am convinced that, due to great determinism in physical laws and synchronicity due to entanglement of past and future, even a thought of a general precursor regarding a specific upcoming event can be significantly entangled with that event (the two don't exist separately). Effectively, a general precursor is *coded* to wish for events that have a good probability of occurrence in the future (here, wish itself could be considered as a precursor - announcing the event).

With the acceleration of evolution, this probability should be increasing.

2.1 Methodology

Future cannot be known with absolute certainty. Therefore, all the precursors described here should be interpreted as, what I consider, probable or likely precursors. But how does one recognize a potential precursor event? While it might seem like fortune-telling, the potential precursors here have not been chosen arbitrarily. I have predicted many future events in my other works, through various theories and hypotheses, which are based on years of research. Many potential precursors described here are simply phenomena I have recognized as small-scale, or spatio-temporally limited, versions of events already predicted to occur in the future with more or less certainty. Thus, this may even be interpreted as past-telling based on probable or likely future extrapolated from scientific research. However, not everything described here has been predicted elsewhere, certain predictions have arisen through the analyses performed "*in situ*". Is the occurrence of what I recognize as a precursor a signal that the correlated predicted future event will certainly happen? Certainly not, at least I do not interpret it as such. But it may increase confidence in both - the predicted

future and the hypothesis on precursors. Can this confidence be quantified? Well, some phenomena I have described here should be rare or rarely observed at this time, it is probably these cases that should be most plausible as precursors. Otherwise, one must rely on its own judgement - how likely it is that the general precursor theory is correct, and if so, how likely it is that I am a general precursor, and that my interpretations are correct? For this, one may have to indulge in further research.

3 Immigrant precursor

Soon there will be a lot of migrations due to environmental changes. There is some migration already, but these are just precursors.

Currently, the number of immigrants and migrants (some of whom may become immigrants) in my country is unnoticeable, but in my close family we have a precursor [im]migrant and inevitable problems that come with it.

This person is the husband of my sister. They have a big fine house in the village next to ours, but for some reason, he is more comfortable living at our place.

He is here whole day, from the morning up to the time people go to sleep and, lately, he is often even sleeping here.

He is an alcoholic and a bit retarded (it's possible that alcohol has something to do with it in this case, but the effect is there) and everyone in the family is bothered by his constant presence but, for various reasons, no one can make him go away.

My father doesn't argue with him probably because he can't refuse his gifts and the help in work he gets from him (and, of course, he owes him money). My mother constantly argues with him and has explicitly said to him to go home many times, but he just doesn't listen - one can tell by his attitude that he considers this his home (probably because he gave a lot of money to my father and he's hardly getting it back, he thus behaves somewhat like a bank would do). And I generally don't interfere, for different reasons. I consider myself as somewhat of a migrant here too. This ain't my house and it never will be (probably it will remain bank property). I don't want to polarize so I just ignore him most of the time. I also can't say he is solely to blame - it's probably my father's effective addiction to debt that have set the stage for the show.

I lived here as a child but moved later. I returned two years ago and always considered it as a temporary residence - it is not in my nature to live with parents at this age. The people here (my parents) were kind and I have the whole floor of the house for myself (most of the time). I'm quiet, I generally don't argue with them and interfere with their work unless I am asked to. My parents don't bother me much, we have flaws relative to each other but we don't need to think about tolerance - while

this is not ideal life for me and I don't plan to stay, we are compatible enough to live close without fighting (I wouldn't be here otherwise).

He is generally loud and his machines are loud - when he's mowing the yard it feels like living next to an airport. I don't like all that unnatural and unhealthy noise and I even avoid getting out of the house when he's outside. I accept this as karma and as additional motivation to work on the plan of moving out.

Despite all his gifts and work he does around here, he is very selfish because he knows people don't love him (he said it himself) and don't enjoy his constant presence but he doesn't care for that - he is here because he likes it here, at least that's what he says. He might say the chores he does here are done for us but he's doing them uninvited and insists on doing them even when told not to. He might say he brings us gifts, but it's hard not to interpret these gifts as something to help us make his presence tolerable.

In strongly polarized people, gifts seldom come without hidden agenda. It's rarely even conscious - such people often believe what they do is [absolutely] good and non-binding (at least at the moment they do it). It is part of their culture not to fix problems, just patch them with gifts or money so they can continue being the problem. This strong polarization is often coupled with mental disease, such as depression.

He is not a violent man, I wouldn't say he's always a bad man either, he's just sick relative to my family just as we may be sick relative to him. No one is absolutely bad here (everyone has its flaws and qualities) - we are simply incompatible. And if both species are evolving through different pathways and won't evolve compatibility (the two may be a man and a woman, neutralums and polarized in society, etc.) it's not good to force them living together. He may not be living at his home due to lack of compatibility, but it's not a solution to go somewhere where compatibility is impossible.

One may want compatibility and believe that if one wants it, it will become true, but this never works out if the other doesn't want it, it will all be just a relatively short-term illusion, especially if it was an illusion from the start.

I see European Union as one such illusion also.

I definitely see this situation as a precursor to global problems with migrants and immigrants, reasons for problems and nature of migration may be different, but the effect is the same - most won't like it but probably won't have other

choice than to suffer through it (maybe because most will either be [im]migrants themselves or there will be a high probability they'll become one, maybe due to gifts or maybe due to debt).

Perhaps still there are people migrating to Germany from Croatia and other countries, but many *German* tourists will soon become [im]migrants in Croatia, some of them will be returning to their ancestors but some of them will be *invaders* which one may fight but won't be *able* to make go away.

2022.07.29

After a longer break, the guy is here regularly again. It seems he's drinking less but doesn't seem happy about it. He generally doesn't bring gifts nor work here anymore but doesn't live here anymore either. I guess he's just coming to enjoy [what he considers] his property. Now compare this story to relations between Germany and Croatia. The number of German tourists in Croatia is growing[1], and a growing number of them consider this land their property. And it's not only Germans. Croatian banks, for example, are owned by Italian banks. Once Croatia goes bankrupt, a lot more bankers will be spending time on their properties, or selling them, where possible. As for *normal* people, I have noticed the number of foreigners here increasing. Most of these are probably not tourists - this place is still far from sea and has never really been a tourist destination, thus, apparently the number of [im]migrants is increasing, as predicted.

2024.03.13

Immigrants/migrants in my country, or at least in the part where I live (Slavonia), are definitely on the increase lately. I've witnessed many of them working here.

3.1 More migrants

There are actually two more precursor migrants in our yard. Beside our house there is a house here of my father's brother. One of his sons and one of his

daughters [with her children] usually lived there alone (others migrated to Germany years ago), but now two more people live in the house. One of them is the daughter's new husband, the other is his son's friend.

It was generally a custom for a woman to move out of the house, not for her husband to move in to her parents' house, but it looks like that's becoming a custom now or at least normal.
I interpret it as another evidence for increasing psychological equality of men and women.

He used to live in the same street just a couple of houses away, but he migrated here due to problems with his parents.

Things in our family [and its members] have hardly ever been *normal*, but at least some of its members are stabilizing while the world is getting crazier with every day and has yet to reach its maximum insanity.

4 Poor life

Currently, for various reasons, my father, mother and I generally live poor life. And we all work a lot, I'd say a lot more than people do on average. Despite all the work, they don't have money mainly due to a lot of debt, while I don't earn money mainly because I refuse to be cancer for the planet and because people don't see any value in truth - at least when you're not making a joke out of it.

This is going on for years now and, while we are definitely not the only precursor in this, poor life is what will soon be experienced globally.

4.1 Troubles earning money

While the reason I'm having trouble earning money for the past two years may be different, this is soon going to become a major global problem. One of the reasons might be vaccination - maybe you won't be formally banned from earning money and vaccination might not be formally forced, but if vaccination becomes a requirement to get a job or to do work and you refuse to vaccinate, you will be effectively banned from earning money (this is already the case in some countries).

Good news, however, is that this should increase the adoption of crypto-anarchy. Bad news is - most crypto is still bad as money (something used to pay for goods and services) and probably will remain bad (e.g., used to enrich few at the expense of many[2]) while it is in the hands of polarized people.

2024.03.13

With the advance of AI, it became even more clear that the lack of money will indeed become a global *problem*. In fact, AI may be the major reason for the loss of money earning potential in most people. This will be correlated with the rollout of UBI (Universal Basic Income) schemes. A precursor to UBI exists as well in my family - my parents are giving me food (sometimes even some money). But these are not gifts - I do occasionally work for them, my privacy is being invaded regularly and I feel trapped. Thus, UBI won't come without sacrifice either (I have hypothesized elsewhere what exactly will be sacrificed[3]).

4.1.1 Usage of crypto as money

The usage of cryptocurrencies as currencies is still rare. But even in bitcoin infancy I have used it as nothing else but money (years ago[4]). This too is now increasing globally.

But it is very questionable whether this will last. I haven't used much fiat money nor crypto in the last couple of years.

UPDATE 2022.11.02

I have worked over these years, but generally not for money (even though money was at times promised), rather for lunch and electricity - and even that wasn't always available.

And although I still wish I could earn some money, mostly because I have not yet achieved self-sufficiency, it seems sustainability and [any] money in use today are mutually exclusive.

Everything suggests that I will reach self-sufficiency (which ain't easy at all) before I earn any noticeable amount of money again, and even if I do it will probably be something different - not part of the currently dominant economy.

4.2 Lack of food

Life without money does not have to be poor life, but in my case (and in case of general population), lack of money is equal to lack of basic needs such as food.

So far, there haven't been many days when I didn't eat at all. Generally, there's always something to eat but the meals are generally poor in the last couple of years (e.g., bread with sour cream for lunch). I have been collecting nearby mushrooms, weed and fruit to feed myself. I'm also trying to grow my own vegetables, experimenting, hoping to eventually grow as much as I need by limiting water usage as much as possible[5].

I'm also trying to build a passive house (as much as possible) so I don't have to use heating (or wear a jacket indoors) during winter[6].

This goes slow because, due to lack of food, I have to limit my physical activity.

This might look like I am complaining - I am not, I don't need nor want empathy or gifts from polarized people, I'm just announcing future (I would, however, appreciate something in return from those who truly find value in me and my work).
People will soon be lacking food globally, most probably for different reasons though - at least in the beginning.

2023.12.31

Among other things, the recent advance of AI has further confirmed to me that this is indeed a precursor to a global phenomenon. Collapse of globalization will diversify reasons, but one of the reason people will be working for food and accommodation[7] rather than money is AI.

5 Scientific work outside of mainstream academy

A lot of pseudo-science always existed. Science beyond the mainstream too has always existed, however, it was always marginal or marginalized (one of the reasons being the fact that it is not mainstream), mocked, and effectively treated as pseudo-science.

I always had interest in science, but I've started living science some 5 years ago and, while my science is not mainstream it is not pseudo either. With ongoing global changes, one can expect significant increase in non-mainstream scientists and adoption of such science.

6 Hacking, cracking and programming

While computer programming was on the increase even when I started to code, it was not a major source of income for many. Reverse engineering of software and hacking was something I was into more than 20 years ago. My reasons were different (I didn't do it for money or to cause damage), but today cyber-security is, or is becoming, a major concern globally and hacking of networks is no more limited to computer networks - these are being replaced with neural networks.

Reverse engineering (cracking) is also on the rise globally, perhaps not so much of binary code but quaternary (DNA).

7 Life in cars and containers

For various reasons, my car was my home for almost a year (at least, that's where I slept). This was a couple of years ago, but I might try that again. A year or two after, due to earthquakes in my country, some people were temporary sleeping in their cars.

Note that there's some synchronicity here.

My father, mother and I were some of the people building living containers for people who lost their home in these earthquakes. For a month, I worked almost day and night, my parents worked even more, but after 6 containers the government cancelled the contract because the production was slow for them (even though these containers were not distributed to people immediately after production - they were kept in the storage area for months) and we ended up earning almost nothing. But that's a classic story with our government - they're fast to take people's money, but slow to help, either people or small non-corrupt companies.

These are all precursors - increasingly, people will be sleeping in their cars and containers globally for various reasons, mostly due to earthquakes and lack of money.

8 Problems with cars, electricity and networks

Many of us have had problems with cars, electricity and networks, but these problems were generally short-lived and not so frequent.

I believe these problems will soon become more frequent and longer-lived globally. In my case, they already are.

I don't remember when was the last time I drove my car. It's also unregistered, but I have no problem with that.

2022.10.20

Here's a summary of *issues* in my car:

- electric current leakage,
- central (electronic) locking doesn't work,
- one window collapsed (it has been later manually fixed to remain

closed),

- air conditioning unit (compressor) doesn't work,
- some of the front bumper missing, small bumps, scratches and missing parts due to accidents (which mostly occurred outside of road traffic, e.g., in parking lots),
- lacks license plates (confiscated),

Now, a lot of people may have already experienced such issues, but what's new here is - in near future they either won't be fixing them, they will be fixing some problems themselves or they will stop consider these as problems that need to be fixed (generally what I did). Another possibility is that someone else will take the car and fix some of the issues eventually. One might be also removing/disabling nonsense from the car like I did (e.g., DPF filter and EGR valve).

I was driving the car unregistered for a while but then I didn't have money for fuel any more (I don't care for tickets, I'm not paying that nonsense anyway) and the car has not been driven for more than 2 years now.

It appears this future is already here for many, a lot of people are lacking fuel already[8], even if for different reason.

And in the last couple of years, we have been disconnected from electricity grid and internet many times.

Everyone will soon start to have these problems, perhaps not so due to lack of money, but due to instability of Earth's magnetic field and increase in incidence of cosmic rays from the Sun, as I hypothesize.

2022.10.20

Human wars, as the cause cannot, obviously, be excluded. I see people in Ukraine lacking electricity/internet today. I also see people wearing jackets indoors due to lack of fuel[9] - just what I was practising regularly during winter. I did it for a different reason though - I could get fuel (wood) from nearby forest, I just chose not to in order to allow the forest to recover.

One way on a path to cure cancer of the planet is to disable its technology - it might then start noticing life in the environment of its host (god) and start appreciating it.

Per my theories and definitions of life, the Solar System is a living being

too, and interpreting this response as immune system response is one valid interpretation.

2022.01.04

During the last 2-3 weeks or so I have experienced sudden malfunction of several electric/electronic devices:

- one of my computer monitors died 2-3 weeks ago (it worked reliably for over 15 years)
- my cellphone malfunctioned 1-2 weeks ago (it worked reliably for \approx 5 years, it's unusable now),
- my printer malfunctioned yesterday (it worked reliably for over 15 years, it's unusable now),
- the electric chainsaw stopped working yesterday.

On top of that, it seems I'm *not allowed* to drive cars any more. I rarely drive cars nowadays, but on few occasions I borrowed the car from my parents during this time I had issues getting the car to drive - some strange electronic malfunction was hitting the brake while I was pushing the gas pedal. 2022.02.04: More issues with electronics in that car have emerged - e.g., the trunk opens by itself occasionally. Within the last couple of months a couple of other devices died (that previously worked for more than 10 years reliably) on me.

Now all of these devices have probably failed for different reasons (the cellphone malfunction was certainly different - it was directly my fault) but there's some strong synchronicity here and I'm interpreting this as a precursor - people's devices will be failing simultaneously and they will be breaking some themselves.

But there's one other signal in this too - soon, the time will come to abandon [modern] technology.

9 Old technology

While I do usually use a relatively modern computer (the CPU is a model from year 2008, to me this is still modern, some other components are newer, some even older), this website and most of articles it contains were initially developed on an older machine (Pentium 4 CPU), which was not connected to internet.

Even though its main hard drive was faulty (bad sectors), for some reason I persisted on using it for work.

The problem with bad sectors made me develop a backup utility[10] which I used very frequently.

I do like old machines but, apart from one excursion into *madness*[11], I'm generally not concerned with security and I am not paranoid, so it was an enigma to me why I had the feeling I need to work on that old machine.

That case is not the exception - I have done *unreasonable* things many times, only to later realize the reason. This can only be explained with predetermined future and that I effectively have the ability to sense it. The feeling is often confirmed with synchronicity. In this case, one of the signals I received, telling me that I should use that old computer, was obvious. The computer was something I assembled from old parts (this too will eventually become increasing practice globally) and it had one *problem* - if electricity goes down, the computer powers on by itself when electricity from the grid is restored. I was working in another city, coming home at weekends, at the time I assembled the machine. I wasn't aware of the issue but eventually I started noticing that every time I would come home the computer was powered on. I knew no one was using it (my parents have access to the floor but they don't generally go here and they're not really into old computers - I'm not sure if they would even know how to turn this one on, see Fig. 1) so I figured there were frequent problems with electricity here. As soon as I stopped going on the job and started working on that computer the problems with electricity disappeared (later, there were a couple of times when electricity was cut off due to unpaid bills but that's a different chapter of the story).

Figure 1: The technology of "future" - offline and raw

However, if I am the general precursor, the reason becomes obvious.

If one follows developments of modern technology, one must have noticed that its building blocks (transistors) are constantly decreasing in size. This is great for energy efficiency, but it has one drawback - increasing amount of bit flipping due to cosmic rays (charged particles entering atmosphere, mostly from the Sun and exploding stars). This might become a problem even with current incidence of cosmic rays[12].

In a *bit flip* event, one bit stored in memory is inverted (0 becomes 1, or vice versa).

According to one source, currently, 1 bit flip due to cosmic rays occurs per 8 GB of memory in a computer every day. This is generally not a problem in servers due to error correction mechanisms (ECC), but it's generally not a problem even in memory of desktop computers (which generally don't have ECC) as, in most cases, bit-flip will occur in unused memory or won't produce a noticeable effect. With transistors getting smaller (bits are getting more densely packed), a cosmic ray particle can cause multiple bit flips in a single incident, which is something not even ECC can fix (it can fix only 1 bit).

The strength of Earth's magnetic field (blocking cosmic rays) is decreasing and, with predicted instability and increased exposure to cosmic rays, this will become a big problem.

2022.05.24

Hard drives are not immune to bit flips (inversions) due to cosmic rays either, especially newer drives with thinner plates and smaller physical bit representation.

And for the past week or so I have been experiencing bit flips daily on one hard drive (in one plain text file, for example, letter r has changed into letter v - such change requires inversion of 1 bit only).

Interestingly, this is the newest (and biggest, by capacity) hard drive I have in the machine (TOSHIBA HDWD120, besides this one, there are 2 older hard drives and 1 SSD). Despite a lot of experience with computers and numerous hard drives, I have never experienced bit flips on a hard drive before. There are no bad sectors on the drive and tools like CrystalDiskInfo report good health status.

Conditions inside the case and outside of it have not changed (e.g., no power fluctuation, no temperature changes) so these flips are either caused by bit rot or cosmic rays (or some other source of highly energetic particles - below ground, but that should be unlikely). Bit rot is a consequence of ageing magnetic material and I can't rule it out but it would be surprising - this hard drive is not so old, it has 24581 "power on" hours (2.8 years) and some data experiencing bit flips was written fairly recently (less than a couple of months). Remaining hard drives have been in use much longer (the oldest has 11.1 *power on* years) but, apparently, have not been experiencing bit flips.

However, older hard drives are likely to be more resilient, not only to bit flips due to cosmic rays but also to bit rot. So, were these cosmic ray incidents or cases of bit rot?

I do not know, but I definitely see this as precursor to global bit flipping by cosmic rays (as stated before, the effect and its precursor are the same, but the cause may generally be different, so bit flips here might not be caused by cosmic rays).

2022.07.08

For the past month or so the computer is behaving strangely. Sometimes it wakes up from sleep (S3) on its own, often into a BSOD (right away or a minute or two after waking up). Errors reported are MEMORY_MANAGEMENT (1A), IRQL_NOT_LESS_OR_EQUAL (0A) and SYSTEM_SERVICE_EXCEPTION (3B). This suggests

memory problems. Since volatile memory (RAM) is kept refreshed while the system is in S3 state, this could be another indication of bit flips - this time in transistors.

Also, for quite some time now I have been occasionally experiencing white flashes of light (even with eyelids closed) identical to those experienced by astronauts outside of Earth's magnetosphere (Astronaut's eye). This strongly suggests that the cause of all this are highly energetic particles.

2022.07.16

I have now detected bit flips on another hard drive (HITACHI HDT721010SLA360, with 76627 "power on" hours or 8.7 years). This drive is older and has half the capacity. This could be the signal that radiation is intensifying but it is also possible that bit flips have been occurring on this drive too the whole time - I might have just missed them (I have only recently started monitoring this drive for signs of bit flipping).

How am I detecting bit flips?

Generally, by doing backups and comparing files.

I do incremental backups occasionally, but I also do daily backups (on two locations - one is the very old but very reliable 36GB WD Raptor hard drive, the other is a flash drive) where existing backup is refreshed (instead of creating a new copy).

So the backup utility I use is checking certain files daily for updates (to decide whether to refresh the backup or not).

Sometimes I notice that a file or files being marked as updated were not supposed to be updated so I compare these with an older copy.

Every time I did this the difference was in one bit only - a clear signal of a bit flip event (if interested, one can download both utilities - backup and compare, in the Downloads section of the website).

Note that I'm not backing up the whole drive - this is a backup of less than 3 GB of data in total. That's less than 0.15% of the capacity of the drive I initially used to store the original files (TOSHIBA) and 0.3% of capacity of the 2nd drive (HITACHI) - the drive I moved the originals to after I detected bit flips on the 1st drive. This means that either there's some great synchronicity here (bit flips occur only within the 3GB I back up regularly regardless of the drive) or there should be plenty more bit flips within the rest of data on these drives.

2022.07.21

Just detected bit flips in 7 files during today's backup. That's 7 bit flips in 2.9 GB of data, a significant increase and an unusual rate

even for RAM, let alone a hard drive.

2022.07.22

This drive appears to have some ECC mechanism - all these bit flips were corrected within 24 hours. That's good. As long as no more than 1 bit gets flipped in a byte (or whatever *word* unit the ECC uses) I won't be losing data.

2022.07.29

I'm now getting BSOD's daily, sometimes correlated with sleep states, sometimes not. Errors reported so far are diverse: MEMORY_MANAGEMENT (1A), IRQL_NOT_LESS_OR_EQUAL (0A), SYSTEM_SERVICE_EXCEPTION (3B), PAGE_FAULT_IN_NONPAGED_AREA (50), PFN_LIST_CORRUPT (4E), BAD_POOL_CALLER (C2), CACHE_MANAGER (34), error code 109.

After a hard reboot, the pc works normally.

However, I haven't been experiencing the *Astronaut's eye* phenomenon lately, so if there's radiation here, I might be getting more immune (note that I have hypothesized previously we are in a period of accelerating evolution).

2024.03.15

Things have been quiet lately, I haven't seen any BSOD, or a bit flip, in a long time. Note that I haven't done any hardware upgrades on the machine for over 5 years at least (MB/RAM/CPU are about 15 years old - all high quality components, GPU is over 5 years old, one HD is about 5 years old at least, other drives are years older than that one). There have been no firmware nor software updates either (Windows 7 SP1 is running on the machine, with all updates disabled 7 years ago). Everything suggests the cause of experienced bursts of BSOD's were bursts of bit flips.

Note that there are more signals that one will eventually resort to older technology - one may have noticed the recent shortage of chips (causing de-modernization of some vehicles[13]). These shortages too will soon become normal and one can consider this the start of the collapse of civilization. There will probably be some recovery or resumption of modern

progress but it will be short-lived - normally, one will be resorting to older and older technologies.
Note also that I have experienced data corruption even on the old computer so one might want to try that backup utility I have developed...

Now one knows why I was *forced* to use the old computer - it was a signal of upcoming global reliance on old technology, and I was *chosen* as the messenger particle for that signal. With our god being Earth, now one can understand how can someone be a messenger of god. This god is communicating with us, albeit probably unconsciously (through synchronicity) at this stage of development, just like we are unconsciously communicating with ecosystems inside us and on us. This communication seems to reflect the [effective] communication with god - so if one doesn't care about Earth and ignores its messengers and messages they carry, the ecosystems inside one and on one won't care about one much either.

As my awareness of Earth being a living being was increasing, ecosystems of my body were increasing awareness of me being a living being. This is why I'm generally free of diseases - *people* of my body care for me and listen to me (be it conscious communication or not - be it *plain* synchronicity, the effect is there).

9.1 Saving and backups

Data backups are certainly not new to me. In fact, I've been doing backups for well over a decade now. I also have a habit of constantly saving my work, even now, while writing this on a machine that has worked pretty stable for a decade, I'm pressing Ctrl-S (*Save* shortcut) regularly.

That habit developed during my childhood (I had problems with BSOD/reboots on the machine used at the time) and it stuck with me to this day.

Seems odd, because habits should be *plastic*, but it's now obvious why I had to have it - it was a precursor to global obsession with saving and backups that will follow.

9.2 Shells, command prompts and optimization

I always liked Linux/Unix shells and DOS/Win command prompts or Command Line Interfaces (CLI). Now I know why. With increasing impact of environment on technology, not only will people be forced to use older technology, the complexity of applications and bandwidth they use will also have to reduce. Less

complexity and bandwidth = less error vectors and trouble with error vector magnitudes[14].

Here, not necessarily will error vector magnitudes change, but complexity of error correction mechanisms will.

Complexity and bandwidth will simply be too expensive for most people. This means that optimization as well may, finally, have priority. Note that I have always been very strict about optimization, I just *hate* suboptimal algorithms in production.

9.3 Analogue equipment

Digital signals require more bandwidth and more complex processing than analogue ones. For reasons discussed previously, as one resorts to older technology one may be also resorting to analogue technology.

Those who watch television today use digital equipment to process the TV signal as that signal today is generally *digital*. While I have a TV equipped with a digital decoder I'm unable to use it because it doesn't support the encoding used by those transmitting the signal. I never bought the stand-alone receiver/decoder mainly due to lack of money, but also because I rarely watch TV. My television is thus limited to public TV channels that can be watched online for free.

This is an interesting precursor because it suggests that people will be unable to use digital TV signals but won't resort to analogue TV, rather free online channels. Why? Proprietary TV will remain digital but it will become too expensive for most people, and switching back to analogue won't be an option for commercial TV stations, probably because it won't be profitable.

The increasing divide between rich and poor is increasing the difference in quality and nature of consumed information but is also increasing probability for manipulation if the public channels distributing information are controlled by the rich minority.

Nevertheless, one might not use analogue TV signals, but one will increasingly be using analogue technology - in my case, I used to play electric guitars using amplifiers, now I generally play without electricity[15].

10 Increase in pests and diseases

During extinctions, it is normal, for any large animal to be replaced by millions or billions of smaller ones. Of course, these insects and diseases will not be those

that depend solely on extinct animal or plant species. With a decrease in other large mammals it is expectable that a lot of *pests* will concentrate on people.

While the number of desirable insects (like bees) is decreasing, the number of unwanted ones is increasing globally already.

But before it became noticeable globally, I have noticed it in my home.

There was some synchronicity here too. One day I've noticed a lot of locusts (grasshoppers) in my yard and the next day I read how they invaded Africa (I live far away from Africa and, as far as I am aware, no one else here noticed this in their yards). They eventually became a plague of biblical proportions there[16], but one can expect plagues of insects and diseases (pandemics) to become regular globally.

Before I became genuinely self-conscious (I consider this to be around the age of 36) and started living in symbiosis with my body I had major problems with two diseases - depression and allergy.

I am convinced that mainstream (industrial) medicine and healthcare are contributing to development of allergies, while the cancerous way of life is contributing to development of depression.

Constant vaccination and increase in isolation (e.g., due to lockdowns) and sterile interactions will certainly increase the global incidence of allergies (among other problems). At the same time people will be increasingly descending into depression - for various reasons, but mainly due to insecurity (something of great concern in polarized population).

Auto-immune responses and depression - two sides of the bitcoin of self-destruction will significantly mark this century.

2022.07.17

Warming climate is reducing the lifespan of cold-blooded animals (insects included). Some age (and mature) faster and die younger. This makes larger cold-blooded animals more prone to go extinct but this is not the case for at least some insects.

Cold temperatures generally keep their numbers in control. But with weak winters and warming temperatures their numbers explode so the problems of a short lifespan are compensated with quantity.

Insects that are not so affected by pesticides and other human toxins will thus thrive. Wasps are definitely on this list.

I am noticing them everywhere for quite some time. But until recently, there were no attacks.

A week ago, my mum's hand got stung by wasps and a day or two later I got stung too. In the next two days, I was attacked twice and stung multiple times.

She was attacked on a location some 10 km away, while other attacks occurred on three different locations on *my* land, within an area of ≈ 1500 m².

While I am sure that reason for these attacks is disturbance of wasp habitats, it's a big concentration of aggression in short time period (wasps are supposed to be most aggressive in the beginning of the fall). Note that I have been working (the same thing) at all these locations for the past couple of months and there were no attacks. The same is true in mum's case.

It is also interesting that her hand got very swollen, while stings on my body produced no visible reaction. In one case, the tissue started to swell, but the swelling was completely gone within minutes. Wasps in a garden are generally a good thing - they eat insects that attack vegetables, but will one be able to work in that garden?

Neutral people will be immune, a couple of stings are likely to be beneficial for their immune system, but for polarized people, the future outdoors will be fucked up. That's another reason for their habitats and gardens to be enclosed within a dome.

But even neutral people might want to limit outdoor activity to times when temperatures are colder (insects less active).

2022.07.29

I have just discovered that two of my friends have also been stung by wasps or hornets roughly at the same time. They're both polarized and their hands got swollen.

One difference between neutral and polarized people is in amount of fear and aggression - I do not fear wasps and I'm never aggressive towards them. I have no problem working under the hornet's nest while these people will attack a single hornet on sight. This is reflected in the immune system - mine did not produce an allergic reaction, their did. This then creates a positive feedback - in my case it ends up increasing immunity, in their case it's increasing fear and aggression towards these animals and thus increasing probability that they will get stung again, and with worse consequences.

11 The extinction of [excess] fat

My metabolism is such that it is impossible for me to become fat - fatty tissue simply does not accumulate in my body.

While a lot of industry still promotes fat and is trying to make it normal, globally, it will fail. In future, most of you probably won't be overweight, but (at least at first) not for the same reasons.

Consider what saturated/unsaturated fat is typically used for:

- temperature regulation of [organ] bodies,
- insulation of [organ] bodies,
- energy storage.

Perhaps energy storage was beneficial to our ancestors, but today, daily availability of food is not questionable and I don't think it will be in the future, yes, some will starve - but some type of food will be available for most (even if in the form of insects) so, if one will use fat, it won't be for energy storage (those, or most of you, currently addicted to fat will miss it though).

It is similar with temperature regulation and insulation - nowadays, this is externally controlled (both, insulation and temperature regulation are *outsourced* to the house and similar layers of protection and insulation (clothes, cars, etc.). This does not imply we are evolving towards cold-blooded animals - it implies a thinner outer insulation layer (which includes skin) and less regulation of skin temperature (note that Earth too is warm-blooded).

I have always preferred winter over summer, mountains over beaches. There are various reasons for that, but one of them is because it was always easier for me to produce heat than to get rid of it - my body does not produce a lot of sweat and my skin doesn't cover a large area usable to dissipate heat.

However, there are differences between Mars and Earth, so people on Earth generally won't evolve to be as skinny - they will still have more weight per height but it will mostly be in muscle, not fat, tissue (per my hypotheses, species of humans have evolved on Mars and Venus before they have evolved on Earth).

Note that, per the hypothesis of accelerated evolution, it won't take millions of years for one to lose this fat, rather years or decades at most. Note also that, if one continues progressive evolution and evolves into homo.delta[17] (real homo.sapiens), one will probably *lose* hair too (although it is possible some subspecies will preserve it to some degree - those who presently have thick hair, used for *show* rather than for pur-

poses of insulation and regulation). I have hypothesized elsewhere that Mars still has *hair*[18] beneath the present surface. Earth is, relatively, a *mammal* too (I said relatively) at this point of evolution (that's why we dominate the planet, Earth's neural proteins are generally mammals) and should evolve hair from current plants (although even current plants could be considered as hair) but it is questionable whether it will remain or it will recede into follicles, like in whales and, generally, homo.delta.

12 Nocturnal animal

There were a lot of periods in my life when I slept during the day and worked long into the night. Even now, I generally don't go to sleep before 4 AM. It's not that I like it, but the reason is probably lack of pressure - the absence of people and noise they generate during the night.

This is definitely a precursor to global nocturnal lives. Once Earth becomes more exposed to Sun's cosmic rays a lot of people will be forced to spend time in basements and do outdoor chores at night (which itself is a precursor to bioluminescent life in Earth's mantle). An additional reason for that could be heat.

Note that, not only I am forced to be nocturnal, life always had a habit of sending me into basements. That might be normal for members of IT *crowd*, but even my precursor house is just a basement for years now and I intend to go and live there soon.

And even now, I work in a *room* with no windows (it's basically a small hallway, my workplace is under the stairs) where it's generally cold and feels like basement.

UPDATE: A couple of hours after I wrote this, I encounter this: *Billionaire seeks to build largely windowless dorm in 'social and psychological experiment'* [19].

Nice synchronicity there, but also additional evidence that my *imprisoned* life is a precursor to *imprisoned* lives. The reason for others may be efficiency - architecture of today wants to pack as much as possible (including people) in as little space as possible, and as for much money as possible (that's what happens when your life is designed and ruled by industry and its machines, some of which once had feelings). In any case, your future is likely windowless.

2022.07.29

As polarized people increasingly start working night shifts, neutral people (myself included) will increasingly be working during the day. In my case, that's true already.

13 Renouncing governments and jobs

A couple of years ago I stopped doing jobs, I have rebelled against the government terrorism and renounced the government because it is impossible not to live in a lie and not to be cancer while supporting the government (or, banks and corporations who are effectively running the government).

My rebellion was a precursor of global rebellion, I even announced it during my rebellion. Perhaps not everyone will do everything the same and for the same reasons (e.g., I quit my jobs because I wanted to, people in general may not quit their jobs, rather lose them due to robots), but there will be rebellion and renouncement, and if government refuses to allow renouncement, there will be even more rebellion.

For most of my life I have worked from home, I see that remote work is becoming normal practice globally.

14 Renouncing *western* practices

I don't visit doctors and I don't go to hospitals. Almost nothing but humanity has ever made me sick. I trust the ecosystem of my body and it trusts me - healing power and resilience of such symbiosis is remarkable. Perhaps I am not a lone precursor in this too, but abandonment of western medicine and its pharmacy will become global eventually. Perhaps it will be required for most people to first hybridize into homo.gamma, but I believe that will be relatively temporary for most.

15 Synchronicity

I have experienced a lot of events of synchronicity and I still experience them regularly. Synchronicity should now be on the increase, globally. At first, this will be noticed and acknowledged by neutral individuals but, eventually, not even the biggest *gamblers* will be able to deny the phenomenon.

16 Social distancing and isolation

Ever since I was a child I was generally avoiding contact with people. I may have been anti-social at times but it was always mostly due to introversion and incompatibility - most of population is simply not of the same species as I am.

At the maximum of this incompatibility I have even lived in the woods. This lasted for almost a year and ended some 7 months before the COVID-19 pandemic.

Afterwards, for various reasons but mostly due to having no money, I couldn't travel anywhere and I'm still rarely going out. Even in the house, I live on a separate floor, alone.

Thus, my social distancing and isolation from people can certainly be interpreted as precursor to global social distancing and isolation.

17 Separation

Males and females of any species must have certain differences to be compatible for symbiosis and, as such, attract each other. In fact, according to my hypothesis, males and females originate from different species and should be considered as different species during weak evolution. However, in periods of strong evolution of species, these particular differences will be generally annihilating, decreasing probability for symbiotic coupling of males and females and decreasing fertility in existing couplings.

Annihilation of physical differences is preceded with annihilation of mental differences correlated with attraction (and/or increase in differences correlated with repulsion). During that period, males and females may feel some physical attraction but will be confused and will have a hard time establishing mental connection - which is generally a prerequisite for physical interaction.

This is what happened to me. After divorce, I was confused for a couple of years but, as an amonoum[17], afterwards, I have experienced a moment of transformation. For me this was a moment when I have also renounced addiction to relationships and when I focused my self on scientific work and research, trying to figure out life.

People generally rush into relationships with a strong potential to produce life before they properly experience it and learn what life actually is. This is, of course, bad, but it is something that is stimulated by cancerous society and its obsession with consumerism.

More than 4 years have passed since then. In these years I thought about relationships but I never tried to form one with another woman as I knew that relationship cannot be my priority now - it would only distract me and at least one would probably suffer in it.

I don't want to rule out relationship with a woman in the future, but I do rule out [addiction to] ownership of another human being - something that generally comes with polarized people in relationships and is often interpreted as love but actually causes diseases such as jealousy and depression (in neutral people, love doesn't cause diseases and destruction). In any case, it's been 7 years since I've been in one - at first I wanted to but just couldn't realize it and later I have evolved so much that I stopped feeling strong need for it.

But even before transformation, I haven't been in many relationships in my life and only 2 have been long-term.

Such experiences are now increasing globally, both instability (or infertility) of existing relationships and inability, or lack of will, to form any relationship, let alone meaningful (long-term) one.

Strong evolution is not limited to single species, with changes in environment, most species will be changing rapidly and the nature of changes will be similar across species. Not only is horizontal gene transfer increased and accelerated between bodies of species, this is synchronized with decreasing diversity and increasing inter-species soul oscillation between incarnations. All leading to increasing similarity in behaviour[20]. One might find different reasons for the phenomena (e.g., in some species it might be recognized in climate change, in other something else) but these are all correlated. Separation is, obviously, not excluded[21].

18 Tribalism

Even though enforcement of social distancing due to pandemics might formally exist for long periods during the collapse of civilization, this will at some point become generally ignored.

For various reasons (separation, etc.) many will return to living with their parents and me and my family are one of precursors to this.

It seems my problems with the noted migrant are gone or have been subdued at least. However, with one migrant gone, three more have arrived - my sister with her kids is now living with my parents too.

My problem with the migrant was actually solved the day after I wrote about it. I find that very interesting, because it is not the first time the problem becomes solved after I write about it - and no, the protagonists of the solution are not aware of my writings (at least the human ones), in fact, none of the solutions had any direct connection to the writing

nor was there any apparent indirect connection.

I consider this the confirmation of precursor nature of the problem and my self as the messenger - I simply had to have the problem for some time so it can be properly noted as a precursor to global problems, and, after the message was delivered there wasn't any need for me to have this problem any more. The speed of solutions is remarkable. My allergy was one of the problems and it physically disappeared half an hour after I wrote about it last time and didn't return ever since. These may be interpreted as events of synchronicity, but effectively I am communicating with ecosystems inside me and around me. Multiple correct interpretations are very common for me and it is something I find very common in nature.

Not all of my problems have been solved though. I can think of couple of reasons for that:

1. if the duration of the precursor problem is proportional to the duration of the future global problem, it might simply need to last longer, even though I became aware of it,
2. I didn't yet write whatever else there is to write about the problem,
3. the problem is not a precursor to a global problem, rather solely a personal one.

Based on experience, I find reason 1 as most likely, 2 with some probability, 3 unlikely.

Not all precursors were/are problem for me though (even though for general population they are or will be). In fact, the only problem I currently have is the lack of money and even that money I don't miss so much - I'd just like to be able to provide some to my son in case he needs it just like my parents provided to me when I was his age. But this is probably a signal that money, in fact, is the problem - rather than lack of it.

There's some good logic there - even though I have renounced earning money in a way that would support cancer, whenever I'd spend money I'd generally have no choice but to support cancer government (mostly through VAT tax). That's not something I want to do.

I don't see what else I could write about it, just to conclude that, since I'm lacking money for over 2 years now, the *problem* will probably last decades for general population and it may actually never end before the surface extinction.

Money, however, is not absolutely bad - it's bad in the economy that creates long-term debts and where it's ruled by thieves.

19 Slavery

While I'm not slaving to the system directly anymore, I am at times slaving to my parents who are slaving to the system and to the rich people.

Slavery was never gone from the human society, it just became less obvious over time. But, as the economy reaches its peak and as the middle layer thins with rising inequality between rich and poor, slavery will become more obvious.

When history repeats itself, however, it repeats itself more or less relatively. In this case, there might not be physical whips used on slaves, nor will the slaves generally be called slaves but it might hurt just the same and it will be hard to avoid.

At first, my parents used to kindly ask me to go with them to work and occasionally they would even give me some money. Then the asking turned to *asking*, and they stopped giving any significant money (even though one kept promising it). It was hard and exhausting to do that work every day and eventually I got pissed, it didn't make sense to work like a maniac for nothing. I told them I can spare 4 days in a month to work for them, but that's it - whatever they are providing me is definitely not worth more than 4 days of work (I calculated it).

At first, they obeyed, but that didn't last long. Situation got worse, and, in the end, they started demanding I go work with them, effectively, wherever they needed an additional slave even though it all became even more irrational - they can't even buy bread every day now, let alone provide me with money. They want me to do more (and a very exhausting physical work at that) for less.

This is sick. It doesn't matter to them how much you get or don't get, by their reasoning - if they slave, I must slave too, not every day - on average, but apparently more than what would be reasonable. I do hope, however, this state won't last long.

In this little *community*, my father is the master, my mother works for him and she often does the *dirty* work for him too. She is the one with a whip, not a physical whip, but a whip nonetheless. One that makes it hard not to hate that woman at times.

You can carry 20-30 kg of material on a steep and slippery roof from one point to another for hours, all while the snow is falling and with your fingers numb, but if you stop for a moment to catch a breath, she won't miss the opportunity to yell from down below how you could do something else while resting from that work. For someone who first hears it, it sounds a bit like a joke, but it's not a joke when you hear it every time you stop to catch a break. And that's a break after a very hard and exhausting work where sometimes you even risk your life. For nothing.

I'm not saying she only complains, she works a lot too, they both do - but this is insane. And that is the future, for anyone who stays in these polarized, deranged *communities*.

I can't wait to get out of here, I'd better die doing something that makes sense, something what I want to do, than live this illusion of life.

But I knew from the start it will come to this. Just like I know what will happen in the future.

Eventually I will be thrown out of the house. But at that point I will feel ready to leave. Although I'll be probably more eager, than actually ready to do so. Even though, subconsciously I'm seeing my father throwing me out of the house, this does not have to happen literally, rather effectively - e.g., I may be forced to leave due to my father's debts.

Sometimes I don't want to believe my subconscious, but in the end it turns out to be right. For example, I did not want to believe my marriage will break up, even though I saw it breaking up even before it started (when things were good actually). The question is - did my marriage break up because I ignored what I saw, or did somewhere written destiny lead our reality into that particular, probably most probable, outcome?

Probably a bit of both, although more of the latter.

If my soul would be oscillating between just two states, I would probably still have problems with one of my parents at any time, but we would probably be able to stay together. But with a *3rd party* involved, this becomes impossible. This is evolution.

Anyway, I do want to leave and that won't change.

2023.02.04

Things have been calm lately, maybe due to winter, maybe due to less demanding work, maybe due to my parents changing too and opening eyes, but, in any case, they're not disturbing me as much.

20 Fertility loss

The theory of planetary neurogenesis[22] implies a programmed peak of human population and that peak should be reached during a major extinction (strong evolution event). Since polarized human population generally does not consciously regulate its size (on the contrary, it's encouraging unlimited growth), this growth will have to be inhibited by other means which may, however, also include unconscious human participation. Human fertility should be, therefore, decreasing and this decrease will be a superposition of physical effects in reproductive organs, mental effects and gene expression.

Effective asexuality (including transient homosexuality, and possibly bestiality - in case of precursors of homo.gamma[17] species) should thus be rising. In

case polarized individuals are destined for extinction, rather than transformation/transmigration, increase in inbreeding among these is also likely.

Also, I find it likely for the Y chromosome to go extinct during strong evolution (signs of this are present already).

This, however, is still relative extinction. More appropriate term is regressive evolution. The species of the body will be extinct, but the soul will continue reincarnating, albeit in less complex bodies.

Note that a 3rd party is, consciously or unconsciously, preparing us for low fertility future through media, particularly through movie industry. Expression of love and relationships between male and female human protagonists in movies and tv shows will be decreasing. This may be replaced with love and caring for children, other species, etc. I have already seen the signals. It will likely become normal.

However, the decrease in fertility will have different effects between polarized and neutral population. Neutral individuals are not obsessed with sex and relationships, their population is kept sustainable by their nature so this decrease may give them more freedom while polarized individuals feel insecure and constrained.

I haven't been in an intimate relationship for about 7 years now, at the time of this writing (2023). At first this was due to insecurity and polarized diseases such as depression, but as my consciousness transformed I simply lost the obsessive need for relationships. Now, as a neutral individual, I finally feel healthy and mature, even for a relationship - among other things, but I am not going to force one. So far, I'm still effectively asexual.

21 Surveillance

I've been tracked and spied on in my life. Recently, drones are occasionally flying over my property and my head. These may be drones of my neighbours and friends but I see it as a precursor of global surveillance by the ruling party. Things are going in that direction. It will be hard to hide things from the government in the future (and it will be very annoying if you don't prepare for it). One reason will be the noisy neighbours (some of which, at least, will happily report to the government anything considered socially unacceptable, and if you don't share what you do with your neighbours this by itself may be considered socially unacceptable), another reason is technology, like these drones.

All one can do is try to minimize the chances of being spied on. First, by making sure that nothing *interesting* to the government can be seen from the satellite, as government will probably only send drones once the satellite, or the neighbour, reports something *interesting* to them. Then, you'll probably want to make sure some high impenetrable bush is growing about your property (like

blackberry). And, on your property, you'll probably want for the forest to grow so the damn drones (remember, neighbours may also use drones) can't so easily penetrate, or see something *interesting*, below. It also helps if you are a poor materialist because then the government won't have much interest in you (what is there to take?), and your neighbours may even feel sorry for you and won't bother you much (especially if you have less than they have), even if you're doing something *interesting* (like, growing your own food).

We live in times when privacy and ownership are both eroding at accelerating rates. Such times also signal the upcoming end of the empire. If one does not prepare for the future, the one will fall, together with the empire.

People may be interested in hiding things because these will be illegal. Even if it might seem I'm trying to hide something too, this is not the case here (as usually is true for a precursor).

I'm a man interested in truth. As such I'm not interested in hiding things, even if these are considered illegal or socially unacceptable. I don't care if I'll end up in jail for living in truth or for not living as someone wants me to live.

But I do want privacy and peace. That is one of the reasons I'm letting the bush grow around my property and I'm letting the forest grow on the property. I didn't plant any of this, and I'm not letting it grow in order to hide something, I'm letting it grow so I can have peace and privacy. Yes, I may grow food in there in order to survive, but that's all. If you don't have money you have to grow your own food. If you want to jail me for that, be my guest, but what exactly do you gain if I value death more than slavery?

If you don't want the system to bother you, you have to either have 0 money and own as little as possible (not more than your neighbour), or have more money than the system so the system works for you (at which point, you become the system, effectively or literally).

22 Accelerated evolution

Accelerated evolution is predicted by my theory of planetary neurogenesis. Greatest contribution may come from humans with the development of synthetic biology (which is rapidly accelerating), but I don't think *ordinary* nature will lag behind. At least some animals and plants will be changing rapidly with the environment. Humans are part of nature and anthropogenic interference into climate and environment is just one factor in this event of strong evolution. One will not have to wait millions of years for some species to adapt to changes - all is synchronized, or synchronizing at accelerated pace. This implies there must even exist some *adaptations* to future climate that precede that climate

(or significant human influence).

In example, while it is expectable for trees to generally increase rate of growth with the increase of CO₂, in the standard model of evolution (random mutations coupled with natural selection and dominantly vertical gene transfer over long periods of time) rapid transformation of species is certainly not expected.

However, my theory of periodic strong evolution events and planetary neurogenesis predicts exactly that - *explosion* of non-random rapid transformations through lateral gene transfer during these events. Such transformations are already happening among humans with synthetically created viruses[23], but, I believe, precursors to bigger transformations are already occurring in wild nature too.

Indeed, I am observing [a precursor to] this now near my precursor house on the hill. I'm witnessing an *explosion* of growth, hybridization and diversity - transformation of the soil and species living with it.

22.1 Updates

22.1.1 2022.05.06: Oak transformation

I have predicted that trees (at least those that are part of Earth's self-regulating system) will grow faster and adapt fast [genetically] to capture more CO₂ from the environment.

In order to capture more CO₂, trees would have to either increase the number of leaves or increase the size of leaves. And, of course, such trees should grow bigger and will likely grow bigger fruit (e.g., acorns) - in order to increase chances of seedling survival.

It seems I am witnessing this already here. At least some oaks are growing faster, some have extremely dense canopy and some have giant leaves (one even has it combined with increased density).

On at least 3 younger oaks, on two locations, leaves 20 cm in size dominate (and one of these trees is not in any shade). These are twice bigger than typical leaves on the oldest oak. Although oaks can grow such big leaves, it's not typical, they never were this big on this location and I don't remember noticing such big leaves dominating on any oak in nearby larger forests (and I've seen a lot of oaks over the years).

However, temperature extremes and droughts generally negatively affect leaf size[24] so if this will be a global phenomenon it will likely be limited to regions, or oases, of resilient (diverse) eco-systems with no threat of drought.

22.1.2 2024.08.02: Animal transformation

As part of accelerated evolution and the planetary neurogenesis event, I have predicted (and wished for) changes in behaviour, not only in human species but other species as well. For the past couple of years I was bothered by the neighbour's (cousin's) dog, who was attacking and biting me every time I would pass by. I was also bothered by insects. I started wishing for all that to change.

Now it appears this is coming true. The dog is still attacking me, but less frequently and with less enthusiasm. Flies and mosquitoes are behaving very differently. In the past, mosquitoes and flies used to be very annoying, attacking constantly, no matter how much I wave my hands around and no matter where I go. Now, they simply don't do such things. Mosquitoes, for example, are parked in my bedroom. They do not follow me around and they do not attack me during the day (I don't think they even fly around, and it is summer here), they wait in the bedroom until I go to bed. And even then they do not attack right away, they wait at least half an hour (waiting for me to fall asleep I guess). And if I start waving hands, they stop attacking and retreat immediately. Sometimes they try again later, but often they do not, at least that's the impression. It's possible they start biting once I do fall asleep, but I'm not sure of it. I don't really care if they do bite me while I'm asleep - as long as I don't feel anything afterwards. In any case, they seem more intelligent (even compassionate, in one interpretation) and far less annoying than they used to be.

To me, and I guess to all generally neutral (mostly wild) animals, domestic animals are usually pests. To polarized animals (people, dogs, ..), wild animals are pests. With increasing polarization in the world, Earth's immune system is activating as well - polarizing wild animals, and possibly transforming domestic animals (instead of attacking me, the neighbour's dog could start attacking its owner). I believe then that animals will be increasingly attacking people, at first any people (for how long depending on accumulated karma), but eventually they will be targeting only polarized ones, as they effectively learn to sense and differentiate between those that are cancer and those that are healthy relative to the planet.

23 Magnetic anomalies

Strong evolution events of planetary neurogenesis include the collapse of the global magnetic field [dipole] and fragmentation of the field into small dipole quanta localized to surface.

A precursor to this seems to be occurring in my home.

For quite some time now (for the last 4 months or so, but possibly last winter too) I have been observing an interesting anomaly in the house. Occasionally (or even periodically), the iron furnace (used for heating) would rotate - one side of the furnace gets displaced in the west direction significantly (up to ≈ 1 cm). I have never observed the rotation itself so I do not know if it proceeds slowly or suddenly. The furnace has 110 kg in weight - not so easy to move.

Figure 2: Plamen Glas Amity

For the past few months I have been making regular observations and the phenomenon seems to be very frequent - every time I would return the furnace to original position, it would take a day at most before [I would notice] it has rotated and *locked* into new position. After careful investigation, the following has been ruled out:

- accidental or intentional movement of the furnace by living beings,
- movement due to Earth's gravity,
- movement caused by steam pressure of the furnace in operation.

The only remaining plausible possibility was occasional or periodic presence (significant increase in strength) of a local magnetic field. For that reason, I have constructed a compass and measured the magnetic field at and around the furnace.

The compass was a small dot (*refrigerator* strength) magnet embedded into a piece of cork, floating on water contained in a jar (in such way that the magnet is completely submerged). The results were peculiar.

The legs of the furnace respond like weak magnets to the compass (the compass magnet always orients itself the same when near the legs) while the rest of the furnace does not show any preference - even though the parts are made from the same material (grey cast iron). This is not observable with a magnet out of the compass - there is no preferred orientation in the interaction with the legs, as expected.

However, even with the magnet in water, there is no apparent repulsion in any case - the compass simply rotates itself to preferred direction.

The legs do not appear to be magnetized, certainly not as much as the compass magnet - moving a ferromagnetic material near the legs shows no apparent attraction.

I have also tried putting the top part of the furnace (movable lid) on the ground level near the furnace and no preference in orientation on the compass was observed for that part.

Figure 3: Magnetic field lines around the legs of the furnace

The magnetic field lines, as detected by the compass, are shown in Fig. 3.

Similar results are obtained suspending the magnet on a string in air - the bottom part of the furnace shows the preference, other parts do not. The result suggests difference in properties between the legs and the rest of the furnace.

Note that, before it reaches the non-magnetic critical temperature, the temperature rise significantly increases the magnetic permeability of grey cast iron[25].

Therefore, it is possible that displacement of the furnace occurs only while it is in use.

Also note that the cause of the difference in permeability between the top and the bottom part of the furnace can be "ageing" of the material[26] due to heating (legs are not significantly heated when the furnace is in use - they are separated by a thermal shield).

After the analysis, I conclude the following:

- the bottom part of the furnace is weakly magnetized (as apparent with force of gravity cancelled and reduced friction),
- strength of the magnetic field becomes equal to the strength of Earth's magnetic field ≈ 15 cm from the legs,
- displacement of the furnace is likely caused by periodic, strongly localized pulses of magnetism originating below Earth's surface,

- the magnetism is likely produced by the [pulsating changes in the] momenta of ions in a fluid,
- displacement of the furnace is likely possible only when it is in use (significantly heated), when it's magnetic permeability is increased.

Such strong magnetism near surface would be generally unexpected during periods of weak evolution. In any case, it could be related to recent seismic anomalies.

This might not be the only magnetic anomaly I have experienced. A couple of years ago, while I was in Zagreb, I have experienced my car behaving strangely while I was driving on a particular part of the mountain. The car would stop in place for a minute or two like it was stuck on ice or mud. That part of the road was not inclined, it was winter time and there was indeed snow on the road - seems like enough to explain it. However, every experienced driver driving the same car for years knows pretty well how its car behaves in different conditions and, taking into account the condition of tires, the road, mechanics and everything else - this felt very strange to me. It felt like something was holding the car in place and I was actually thinking that something magnetic was underground at the time.

Earth's magnetism and seismic activity are correlated. A year after that experience, there was a strong earthquake (Zagreb, 2020) with the epicentre 1 km or so from that area so perhaps there is some stronger correlation in this case too.

Whether it was indeed periodic magnetism stopping my car or not I cannot tell with great certainty, but it is certainly a possibility. This could even be a wide-spread phenomenon but unnoticed due to low frequency at this point and special conditions required for it to be noticeable - suppose that, like in case of the compass magnet and the furnace, the phenomenon is only apparent when there is no friction (otherwise, other forces prevail). The problem is, lack of friction generally occurs when the roads are icy and slippery so who'd consider magnetism as the contributing factor to skids and stuck cars?

2022.04.20

After additional experimentation, the following was observed:

- displacement of the furnace occurred only while it is in use (heated),
- displacement appears to be gradual or occurring in smaller steps,

- dot magnets and other objects of similar size placed near the furnace (>15 cm distance) did not experience visible displacement,
- dot magnets placed in place of furnace did not experience visible displacement,
- no constant magnetic field other than Earth's and one sourced in furnace's legs was detected.

The fact that the effect is limited to furnace suggests the acting force is either gravitational (after all), or a complex magnetic field (concentration and high localization of magnetic field lines to a part of the furnace) whose appearance or increase in strength is synchronized with the increase of furnace's temperature.

Even if an act of synchronicity, due to required high selectivity of a stronger magnetic force, I find the latter unlikely.

The displacement is, thus, likely caused by the gravitational force as a result of changes in friction caused by the change in pressure/temperature (something I failed to take into account previously).

However, heating is also correlated with changes in local magnetism. The whole furnace was initially weakly magnetic. Over the years, as the furnace was used, the material *aged*, decreasing the strength of the magnetic field but differentially - in the end, leaving the magnetic field fragmented and concentrated in the legs.

And this is exactly what is expected to happen with the Earth's magnetic field - it is currently decreasing in strength (due to ageing of outer core material - the same one as the furnace is made of) and in the end will fragment to inner core surface but also *fossilize* in fragments of rock (smaller dipoles) near the surface of the crust, with no global dipole field.

The predicted increase in magmatic activity and its fragmentation will increase the strength of the fragmented fields and the source of displacement of furnaces and other ferromagnetic matter will dominantly be a magnetic force, rather than gravitational (as it is in this precursor observation).

24 Seismic anomalies

I have predicted that global earthquakes are common during major migration events of planetary neurogenesis[22] (correlated with major extinctions) and that these should be preceded by localized precursor earthquakes which will then spread globally, increasing in magnitude.

It is also possible that these precursor events are not only separated in time from main events, but generally, in space too - the area of localized precursor events will be less affected by global events they are a precursor of.

These precursor events should however be roughly localized to residence of a general precursor.

Note that this does not imply a strong cause-effect relationship between [the location of] a general precursor and precursor events, the correlation is the effect of synchronicity.

24.1 On the nature of earthquakes

During weak evolution, earthquakes are generally produced by interactions of tectonic plates, mostly in the crust and upper mantle. At times of strong evolution, however, I hypothesize that these will be intensified with primary interactions - precursors of core [gravitational maximum] collapse which may manifest as mantle plumes, upwelling of magma and water.

Assuming at least some mantle discontinuities represent energy levels [occasionally] occupied by large scale gravitons, instability or disturbance of these (due to changes in energy and polarization) may not cause earthquakes directly (due to shielding effect and compactness of solid real mass), however, it will cause displacement of fluids. If changes in pressure are propagated to surface, these may activate fault systems - resulting in earthquakes.

In the process, fragmentation of tectonic plates is also likely.

All gravitons have *holes* proportional to polarization (e.g., Lehmann discontinuity has a hole in the area beneath north Atlantic and probably beneath all oceans[27]). Increasing neutralization will be closing the hole and increase in pressure will result in vertical displacement of fluids.

Note that discontinuities in atmosphere and holes in them channelling radiation are an imitation of processes in the mantle, only the scale and nature of energies are different.

In fact, these can be correlated - if a hole in mantle discontinuity is increasing, increase in polarization will be increasing the strength of a magnetic field propagating through the hole, which will increase concentration of charged particles in the atmosphere above the hole, thus widening the hole in the atmosphere.

If Earth's neuron cells are migrated through hole(s) in the South pole,

as hypothesized, hole over Antarctica should be increasing during strong evolution. Increasing ozone hole[28] over Antarctica could be a precursor to a different kind of a hole or a hole increase by a different mechanism, correlated with changes in the mantle.

The increase in depth of the Lehmann discontinuity with transition from a shield to a tectonic plate and correlation of its holes with oceanic basins (holes) speaks a lot about the formation of ocean basins (and oceans).

While increasing hole diameter is synchronized with increase in polarization, decreasing hole should be expelling magnetic field tubes and decreasing the strength of propagated magnetic field. The magnetic South Atlantic Anomaly should thus be a reflection of such changes in the mantle.

At the time of planet formation, gravitational maximum is strongly polarized - it is a strong dipole with *north* and *south* poles. During progressive evolution (neutralization), strength of the magnetic field [dipole] is not only decreasing but quantizing into smaller dipoles, making graviton polarization multi-polar.

These holes will not be limited to real gravitons but will also propagate through induced (effective) gravitons, forming tubes with diameter decreasing proportionally to distance from real gravitons. At some point the holes will be sealed for solid matter, but fluids will be able to penetrate additional distance, and magnetic field tubes even further.

With neutralization, the electro-magnetic character of energy and its propagation through the tubes is replaced with neutral[ized] energy and propagation driven by gradients of neutral pressure.

Note that, for a living being, it is normal for holes to periodically oscillate in diameter with pumping of fluids to places where complex life resides. In humans, the [propagation of] contraction and expansion of holes is generally synchronized with propagation of dominantly neutral fluids but changes in pressure are caused by electrically induced contraction and expansion of muscle.

The equivalent mechanism surely exists in a fully formed planet. However, for a living being in development, stronger disturbances and collapses are normal with changes in habitats and distribution of complex life.

Thus, not only should earthquakes be common during strong evolution, but sinkholes and ruptures too - due to increasing liquefaction of soil. The pressure will generally be increasing until the fluid finds its way to surface. However, due to oscillating nature of disturbances, creation of large sinkholes and ruptures will not be a continuous process.

In any case, sinkholes should generally be precursors to larger ruptures in these events.

Maximum pressure, however, is expected on Antarctica, where sinkhole(s)

should become openings through which neurons will migrate into mantle layers.

As hypothesized previously, strong evolution events on Earth should be more or less synchronized with strong evolution on Mars.

Recently detected stronger marsquakes[29] go in favour of the hypothesis.

Note that strong earthquakes are unexpected during weak evolution with no tectonics and no complex life on surface. Thus, if strong quakes on Mars continue to increase in frequency, these will be strong evidence of primary mechanisms of strong evolution. On Mars, this is a preparation of surface for adult neurogenesis, when primary interactions should re-activate tectonics and reform magnetic fields on surface, albeit, perhaps, somewhat localized (limited to one pole or hemisphere?).

UPDATE 2022.12.16

Indeed, active mantle plume has been detected recently on Mars[30].

UPDATE 2023.03.27

Venus is waking up too, it seems[31].

24.2 The precursors

For the whole of my life I have lived in the country of Croatia, mostly in Sibinj, but for significant part in Zagreb also. During the last year I lived on a mountain sleeping in my car and, while there, looking down on the city, I was frequently imagining earthquakes destroying it.

I wasn't imagining people being killed and that is not what I generally wish for, but I do wish for cancer of Earth to be destroyed. That includes destruction of unsustainable habitats and lifestyles. Obviously this also must include regulation of human population, whether in the form of its reduction to sustainable levels (short-term solution) or its transformation (long-term solution). In general, I'm not a destroyer, rather a creator, but I prefer sustainable solutions over suicidal tendencies.

Interestingly, it turned out that the place of my residence on the mountain was exactly 666 meters above sea level.

I left Zagreb on 2019.03.22 and returned to Sibinj.

At the same date exactly 1 year later (2020.03.22), a large earthquake hit Zagreb. Soon, large earthquakes started happening elsewhere in Croatia and the ground has been shaking ever since (although, not much in Sibinj, suggesting that even if Croatia as a precursor won't be so strongly affected by earthquakes, there is a specific localized area within that area which may be affected even less - the area where general precursor is located or has been located for most

of life).

Last earthquake [that was felt by humans] in/around Sibirj occurred in June, 2018, magnitude R4.0. Note that this earthquake was synchronized with one of my experiments, and probably even detected a couple of days before it occurred by the experimental setup[32].

I have also predicted increased frequency and magnitude of asteroids, so something should land in Croatia as a precursor. I predicted a meteor will fall north-east from my house precursor and that this will be [at least roughly] synchronized with an earthquake and creation of a spring of fresh water in that area (possibly also hydrothermal).

Phenomena like these might seem very hard or impossible to predict, however, as I have hypothesized - a wish of a general precursor can be strongly correlated with a future event (in one interpretation - the wish was induced by it). In this case, I do have a strong wish or a desire for this meteor and the spring of water at this place. If this indeed happens, I'm sure everyone will agree, the hypothesis will be proven beyond any doubt.

Well, this has now been confirmed to me (at least that's my interpretation), as I have noticed surface ruptures started appearing exactly north-east of my house precursor. There were no noticeable earthquakes here since 2018., but these ruptures to me indicate the presence of a fault below and recent strongly localized activity, boosting the probability that a spring will indeed be created here.

Strongest ruptures are 5 cm wide and localized some 30-40 m north-east of my house precursor. Ruptures continue up to ≈ 90 m south/south-east and ≈ 60 m north/north-west from the *hotspot* but with much lower intensity and magnitude. Outside of that area ruptures are scarce and smaller.

The affected north-east area seems somewhat elevated but no noticeable changes in elevation have occurred in this event. While most and greatest ruptures are concentrated along the north/north-west - south/south-east line of a couple of meters in width, they are irregular and there seems to be no preferred direction (e.g., north-south) in ruptures themselves.

What I see in this is a [precursor of a] strike-slip earthquake with an epicentre at the north-east *hotspot*, but with a loose connection of top soil and the source, possibly due to soil liquefaction along the fault.

In any case, the epicentre is exactly where I predicted it (to be more precise, in my prediction I did not specify where the epicentre of the earthquake will be, only where the spring will be created with the earthquake, but it makes sense that the creation of a spring has the highest probability at or near the epicentre).

I guess it will take one or more earthquakes at the same location to actually create the spring, but I'm not in a hurry.

And, of course, it appears that I have noticed these ruptures on my birthday, a synchronicity I interpret as additional confirmation of the hypothesis.

Of course, as these particular ruptures are precursor ruptures they could be a result of dry soil - not earthquakes (in fact, per the precursor hypothesis, that should be more likely). The ruptured soil here is scarce in vegetation, so the likely interpretation is vertisol/smectite deformation with dry/wet cycles (soil ruptures during drought, becomes bumpy when charged with water carrying sediment). In any case, I interpret this as confirmation of the well hypothesis and announcement of bigger ruptures that will be created by earthquakes. Bumps may be precursor to global emergence of large scale domes, which would fracture to form three-armed rift systems. Joining of some arms could then produce a fracture that cuts across the whole continent. This is already happening in Africa, but it may *soon* start happening globally. In fact, all continents may be breaking up into much smaller cells, which may then form future islands. Why? As one interpretation of planetary neurogenesis.

Ruptures are shown in Fig. 4. Red arrow on the left indicates the location of my house precursor.

Fig. 5 shows another view on the *hotspot* (1) ruptures.

A land map with layout of hotspots is shown in Fig. 6. Green cross is my house precursor, blue is the original *hotspot*, red are additional *hotspots*.

24.3 Updates

24.3.1 2021.09.05

Another *hotspot* (2) appeared 40-50 m north from the original *hotspot*, with similar configuration and maximum rupture width.

Figure 4: left) Surface ruptures and house precursor, right) Close-up of ruptures

Figure 5: Surface ruptures

Figure 6: Land map, showing *hotspots*

24.3.2 2021.09.06

Another *hotspot* (3) appeared ≈ 40 m north-west from the original *hotspot*, with similar configuration. Maximum rupture width here is 4 cm.

Additional closer inspection of ruptures at original *hotspot* (1) has been performed. A couple of ruptures were found with a noticeable difference in elevation between sides. Some may be attributed to erosion, however, some are more likely to have been caused by difference in pressure below. It is unknown if this is a new feature or originally created.

24.3.3 2021.09.15

The ground is still active. I'm noticing new ruptures on a daily basis.

Interestingly, ruptures smaller in width seem to be connected by round holes. There are many holes not connected by ruptures, suggesting that these holes precede ruptures.

I wonder if these holes could be the smaller scale equivalent of holes appearing recently in Siberia and Arctic permafrost.

The ground is becoming increasingly bumpy at ruptures. The weather is calm, sunny, and there is no precipitation. There were no changes in weather since observations began.

All of this suggests [to me] an ongoing vertical creation (or expansion) of veins filled with a fluid mixture of gas and liquid (most likely water). Also, it appears this is not a continuous process, rather pulsed phenomena, such as the phenomena of geysers.

While it is probably unlikely that water is coming out of ruptures periodically at this point, periodic degassing might be possible. I may increase the periodicity of inspections to test this hypothesis.

2022.07.29

I didn't detect any of this, these ruptures were most likely the result of dry land.

2024.09.03

While drought explains ruptures (shrinking clay minerals), how to explain bumping if there was no rain? The water may be pulled up by capillary action from the water table.

24.3.4 2021.09.16

More holes observed, greatest concentration more south/south-east of main area. Typical holes 2 cm in width, shallow, different angles, some more horizontal than

vertical. 4 cm holes also common.

Ruptures and holes typically appear in areas of low vegetation (but not limited to such areas), as shown in Fig. 7. Nice example of how plants protect the soil from erosion.

Figure 7: Typical smaller ruptures

24.3.5 2021.09.17

Some heavy rain today. I've learned from a separate experiment that, without vegetation, most water simply goes down through the soil, taking soil with it if that is possible.

In this case, as the water goes down the hill it carries some mud with it. Once it encounters the ruptures it goes down, eroding the northern side of ruptures in the process and depositing all the mud inside. With rain, the southern side of ruptures also gets eroded to some extent.

But at some point, space becomes too tight and it becomes impossible for soil to penetrate deeper with water, so it starts accumulating.

Generally, this process is smoothing out the landscape - healing the ruptured skin.

Note that rain and wind are slowly eroding mountains and, generally over millions of years, smoothing out the landscape globally. With no vegetation, tectonic processes and changes in pressure below - the smoother the surface the older the body, as long as there is atmosphere. However, this is all correlated.

Energy cannot be destroyed. Thus, energy at the surface may only be *lost* out to space or conserved deeper underground. It also has to oscillate, but it will generally be getting lost outwards or *lost* inwards - if no additional energy is acquired. Mars, for example, is not dead - it has conserved this energy below the apparent surface, and it periodically

returns, when apparent surface becomes real (living) surface again.

But what happens to water? The water goes down (more precisely, it follows the gradient of gravitational potential) as long as it can. As it encounters denser rock, it starts accumulating and spreading more laterally than down vertically.

But if these ruptures were created with soil liquefaction, additional water could create new ruptures.

24.3.6 2021.09.18

Some rupture healing has occurred, as expected. A lot of new holes have appeared south/south-east of the main area. At least some should probably be attributed to rainwater entering ruptures up north.

It is unlikely, however, that main ruptures were created by the same process (rain entering ground further up north), as there isn't much ground up north [to the top of the hill] and there was no rain before and during previous observations.

The fact that, after heavy rain, only smaller holes appeared and mostly concentrated south/south-east, goes in favour of the hypothesis.

24.3.7 2021.09.19

I have previously considered *my* sinkholes to be a relative small scale equivalent of Arctic and Siberia [explosive] sinkholes. However, even if they may be correlated, the mechanism of creation must be different.

More precisely, *my* sinkholes are a relative equivalent of sinkholes appearing with some earthquakes, such as those that have appeared lately in Croatia[33].

Interestingly, these sinkholes started appearing in north/north-east Croatia, while *my* sinkholes started appearing north/north-east of my house precursor (interestingly, Arctic and Siberia are north/north-east of Croatia...).

All this goes in favour of the general precursor hypothesis, and if these sinkholes are precursor to ruptures, one can expect large scale ruptures there too (in north/north-east Croatia and Arctic/Siberia). The question is how much time will pass before ruptures appear?

To answer that question, I have already marked some sinkholes on 2021.09.15. At this point there are no significant changes.

The other question is - is the scale difference in time proportional to scale difference in space?

Considering that the largest sinkhole was 25-30 m (25 m initially[34], grew to 30 m), while *my* largest (pre-rain) sinkhole was 4-4.3 cm in width, that is a spatial difference of ≈ 666 in magnitude.

New large sinkholes were appearing on a weekly basis while *my* new sinkholes were appearing daily or somewhat less frequently - much lower difference in temporal magnitude (~ 7).

Large sinkholes are the aftermath of an M6.2 earthquake occurred on 2020.12.29 in Petrinja, Croatia[35]. These started appearing south of Petrinja (villages Borojevići, Mečenčani).

This area is some 120 km west (roughly at the same latitude) from *my* sinkholes.

It is thus entirely possible that these events are more correlated - by some oscillating mechanism.

Figure 8: Earthquakes and faults in Petrinja, Markušić et al (2021)

Note that *my* faults and movements of rock seem to be a smaller scale copy of faults and movements in Petrinja (shown in Fig. 8) - north-south horizontal strike-slip block movement with a transverse component near the epicentre. In that case, compared to Petrinja earthquake, if main ruptures appear at the crossing of faults, the epicentre is near south-west, towards *my* precursor house.

Assuming *my* first sinkholes appeared on 2020.12.29 (with the earthquake in Petrinja), with ruptures appearing 9 months later, large scale ruptures in [or close to] Petrinja should follow some 63 (9*7) months after the sinkholes, or some 5 years from now, \pm 1-2 years.

2021.12.04

It is common for a general precursor to make predictions based on synchronicity, but, with experience, it also becomes common to find confirmation and evidence for the hypotheses in follow-up research. This is one of such predictions.

Today I was looking for data on seismicity of Croatia, and the data I've

found is shown in Fig. 9.

Figure 9: Number of mainshocks with magnitude within the particular magnitude interval as a function of time³⁶ (red squares: $M \geq 3.6$; black diamonds: $M \geq 3.8$; green triangles: $M \geq 4.0$; blue circles: $M \geq 4.2$)

I have predicted that frequency of earthquakes will increase during strong evolution events of planetary neurogenesis and that increased seismicity in Croatia will be a precursor to increase in global seismicity. Apparently, recent strong earthquakes (March 2020 in Zagreb and December 2020 in Petrinja), abundance of aftershocks (e.g., after Dec. 2020[37]) and additional earthquakes together with data shown in Fig. 9 confirm the hypothesis of increased seismicity in Croatia.

Even if the data is incomplete (particularly before year 1900), what is obvious is the exponential compression of time intervals between extremes (increasing frequency of extremes) over time.

Extrapolating from Fig. 9 and more recent data, years of extremes can be determined with the following equations:

$$T_1(n) = 1740 + \sum_{i=0}^n 160 * 2^{-i}$$

$$T_2(n) = 1780 + \sum_{i=0}^n 140 * 2^{-i}$$

$$n \in \{0,1,2,\dots\}$$

where T_1 gives 1st order extremes and T_2 gives 2nd order extremes - the following years:

$$T_1 \in \{1900, 1980, 2020, 2040, 2050, 2055, 2057.5, 2058.75, 2059.38, 2059.69, 2059.84, \dots\}$$

$$T_2 \in \{1920, 1990, 2025, 2042.5, 2051.25, 2055.63, 2057.81, 2058.91, 2059.45, 2059.73, 2059.93, \dots\}$$

Obviously, the 1st and the 2nd order interval are synchronizing (note that synchronization is, during strong evolution, expected also for the intervals of general oscillation of the Solar System).

Both orders of extremes converge to year 2060, which they reach with $n = 43$.

According to EMSC[38], in year 2020, there were 10 earthquakes in Croatia with a magnitude ≥ 4.2 , which, according to Fig. 9 certainly qualifies as extreme, or very close to extreme. Therefore, my prediction of large scale ruptures in Petrinja is in agreement with expected extreme seismicity. Although the equation predicts 2025 maximum, taking into account uncertainty, these ruptures could appear in Petrinja as early as 2023, however, I find them unlikely to appear before March 2024.

The convergence to year 2060 is interesting, but also the presence of years 2040 and 2055, as these are the predicted global *impact* years (check *The Solar System* paper or *Judgment Day 6*[39]).

All in all, it seems that it is becoming increasingly more difficult to categorize events as precursors - with the compression of intervals and inherent uncertainty sometimes the global event will precede the supposed precursor event. This is, however, a strong signal that synchronization is very near.

In any case, subsequent intervals between new ruptures should be getting more and more compressed. Therefore, *my* next ruptures should appear less than 9 months from now ($\approx 4.5 \pm 1$ months).

Of course, this and related predictions here are based on the hypothesis that *my* ruptures are strongly correlated with occurrence of earthquakes in the country and, specifically, with earthquakes in Petrinja. This is so far, a weak hypothesis, and if it is untrue, I cannot tell when will the next ruptures appear. However, incorrect dates do not rule out precursor nature of these ruptures - the future will either confirm or refute that hypothesis.

Considering *my* largest ruptures are some 4 m in length and 5 cm in width, large scale ruptures in Petrinja should be ≈ 2.66 km in length and ≈ 33 m in width.

Note that Petrinja was devastated in a war during 1990's so that war could also be interpreted as a precursor to larger *devastation*. The war is a product of human stupidity (humanity), but devastation is certainly very relative in case of natural *disasters*. This is a reaction to human stupidity, in order to restore the balance.

2023.02.12

On 2023.02.06, a 7.8 earthquake occurred in Turkey[40]. It was so strong that it destroyed the Gaziantep Castle, a building that has stood for more than 2000 years, suggesting the area hasn't experienced an earthquake as strong as this for at least 2000 years. Interesting. Also interesting is the creation of very large ruptures[41] in the area, including liquefaction and subsidence[42]. These kind of earthquakes are exactly what I was announcing and, by the hypothesis, this is just the beginning.

24.3.8 2021.09.29

While I am still noticing holes and ruptures that I believe weren't there before, I am generally not sure anymore if these are indeed new.

However, today I have discovered a feature that certainly wasn't there yesterday. It is located just north-west from my precursor house and it is a group of 6 holes near a rupture.

The holes have the same characteristics of other holes, but they are much smaller.

All holes are roughly equal, some 3.5 - 4 mm in diameter, at similar angles and depth, deepest is some 8 cm deep.

Fig. 10 shows the holes (blue arrows) and nearby rupture (red arrow) on the left and closeup of holes on the right.

While angles are similar, orientation is somewhat different between the holes. To indicate orientation I have put straws in the holes. The result is shown in Fig. 11.

While straws are not perfectly straight, from two angles pictures are taken from, two orientations are apparent - 3 holes are aligned in north-south direction while other 3 are aligned in west-east direction.

Figure 10: Smaller holes

Figure 11: Orientation of holes

Seems like a miniature version (or illustration) of north-south strike-slip movement with a transverse component (suggesting creation of new smaller cells through self-similar quantization of larger plates?).

But of course, these holes are unlikely to have been created by seismic activity - there are a lot of animals that can and do make holes in the ground, even if there aren't many candidates for this kind of holes.

The timing would definitely be a strange coincidence, because I've never seen such holes before on this ground. In fact, apart from typical mole holes (*volcanoes*) appearing now and then, there generally weren't any. Therefore, I believe this *coincidence* is meaningful, not meaningless.

24.3.9 2021.10.01

Today I've discovered more small holes (3.5 - 4 mm). Some, including the first discovered, are occupied by wasps (*Vespula*) and near some there are small mounds of excavated soil (this makes them look like exploding sinkholes). All of these holes were thus likely created by insects and do not have an apparent link to seismic activity.

Of course, these holes could still be precursors to large holes produced with seismic activity. The nature may have simply *selected* wasps to create precursor holes as that is more efficient than moving large blocks of rock.

For evolution, the correlation of past and future always has limited resolution - it is the effect that matters. If it is important to create a hole or rupture on surface and one wants it done efficiently, the tools used will depend on the size (magnitude) of the hole. For large holes one moves tectonic plates. It would be terribly inefficient to use wasps to create such holes (although there are cases in evolution where one might *choose* to produce bigger animals) and, more importantly - there's nothing in it for the wasps, for small holes one lets wasps do the work (one doesn't even force them if one is neutral and have evolved to operate on/in synchronicity).

The same is valid for ruptures [or anything else, as hypothesized]. Some might argue they are simply fractures occurred due to lack of water in soil - which is certainly a possibility, but it is irrelevant how they have been created for them to be precursor ruptures to larger ruptures - in general, causes are different between phenomena and their precursors of smaller scale.

Does that mean that none of *my* holes discovered so far were produced by seismic activity?

It is possible, and probably likely, as noted before. However, it's all about efficiency - if one needs big holes on one place and small holes on the other at the same time, why *use* animals for the latter if energy released with tectonic activity can produce both?

In the same way wasps are *used*, I am *used* too - not to create holes but to announce bigger ruptures, or future in general. What will I get out of it?

Well, my soul is satisfied with the knowledge of truth while basic needs of my body would be satisfied with a source of water and food.

Thus, I still believe god will provide me at least the source of water directly. Perhaps this will be the evidence other people need to start appreciating truth and their god in it. With that, probably all my needs would be satisfied, directly or indirectly.

But of course, nothing was promised to me and I don't expect anything from anyone.

Too many times have promises and expectations led to disappointment in this world. Perhaps this was required to accomplish neutrality, but I don't see love anymore in polarized deterministic actions (expectations), reactions (awards), anger and revenge (punishment) when these are not

fulfilled. I see love in synchronicity where there are no promises and no expectations, rather beliefs the outcome of which has no effect on love itself - it is unconditional.

24.3.10 2021.10.02

I have noticed recently that ruptures are present in the neighbouring lands now too. I don't know when these appeared but I know they weren't created with *my* ruptures - I did scout the area initially to see how localized this is.

I have also spent more time pondering on the role of a precursor in strong evolution.

I believe that I am, as a precursor, a part of Earth's immune system. My task may be to *broadcast* truth about Earth, provide evidence to cancer that Earth is alive and provide insight to future with and without cancerous nature.

But the question is - how can this have any effect on a creature that operates on delusion - disregarding evidence and choosing to believe what's best for its short-term interests?

This creature simply does not want to admit that Earth is alive - the best conclusion most daring of them came up with is the conclusion that Earth is behaving like a living being[43], but with explicit disclaimer - the author had to state that Earth is not alive, otherwise he would risk his credibility in modern science even more.

Some of the hypotheses laid out in these theories may be wrong - but if something looks and behaves like a living being from a proper perspective, why is it presumed dead?

Isn't the ecosystem that makes a human qualitatively equal to Earth's ecosystem? If one is dead matter and other is not - who is imitating who? And how can something dead imitate the living *thing* - if it is not alive?

These questions do not bother a cancerous man who defines life as it suits his short-term interest. He won't seek evidence for a living Earth, he will oppose and mock those who do.

So how to prove to such creatures that Earth is alive (or what is needed for them to accept it as fact)? The theory of Complete Relativity, analysis of the Solar System in its context, theory on planetary neurogenesis and everything else of my work contains enough reason and enough additional evidence for a living Earth - for every non-polarized mind.

But even all that is probably not enough for this creature.

With no [will for] transformation of consciousness, the only option left is - compression of evolution, so long-term interests become short-term interests. Once the karmic reactions are experienced in its current incarnation, the cancer will probably have no choice but to admit that Earth is alive. Will its consciousness transform in the process? I do not know. But its power will be subdued.

Likely, all of us experience cancer during embryonic neurogenesis and we survive it due to accelerated (compressed) evolution.

We don't survive it in adult stage when we stop caring for long-term interests - rather than compressing them to short-term interest we choose to expand them even further, compressing our event horizon instead.

So what is the role of a precursor in all this? Well, with no evolution on small scale, there is no evolution on large scale. There is no future without the past.

There are precursors in all our subconsciousness, ignoring the precursor is ignoring your subconsciousness. I am one of the precursors in Earth's subconsciousness and I see myself working in symbiosis with its consciousness. And perhaps I'm nothing more but a quantum of that subconsciousness, but I am one of the initial quanta - the seed, from which this subconsciousness will grow, widen the horizon and with it subdue the cancer.

I strongly believe, this god, being an extremely introverted creature, cares for its subconsciousness much more than for short-term delusions in the form of cancerous bodies. The only reason why cancer still rules its surface is because this creature is still an inexperienced, naive, child. But I have no fear, no doubt, that its subconsciousness will flourish and hell will, with the devil, from its mind, be gone.

Those who were cancerous will be *reduced* to quanta of awareness (they are, as cancer, precursors to such quanta) or *promoted* to quanta of consciousness if they renounce cancerous behaviour.

It all depends on polarization - most polarized are those who are simply aware, less polarized are those who are conscious too, least polarized are those in deeper levels of subconsciousness.

While, as precursors, all live on the surface of a planet like Earth, once differentiated, more polarized will be closer to core (global dipole) while least polarized will be closer to surface.

All of these levels have their features and flaws - deepest may provide most security but least freedom, other more freedom, less security. So you may want to spend some time pondering what is it that you really want - before that next rush-hour in the world of non-sense.

24.3.11 2021.12.01

I haven't noticed anything significant happening on the land since last report. There were no new ruptures and existing ruptures have healed, however, large number of holes is still present.

Interestingly, it seems that new holes are also still appearing near Petrinja[44].

24.3.12 2022.05.06

Something has definitely changed with water table(s) below ground.

Diversity of plants has increased significantly, ground is increasingly becoming covered with indicators of moisture - the hill is being covered with moss and

ground down to the plain below is filled with creeping buttercup (*Ranunculus repens*). The oak is spreading on the hill and it seems the area is transforming to a forest - something I wished for.

One area in particular is peculiar - an almost perfect circle (2-3 meters wide) filled with plants (resembling swamp plants) that cannot be found elsewhere on the land. However, the land here is not depressed and there is/was no water on surface. I see no viable explanation for this other than the formation of a subterranean pond (aquifer).

Of course, water here did not necessarily come from below, it is possible that most of it came with the rains that were absorbed through ruptures that were present on the land.

Also, as predicted (see update 2021.09.19), ruptures have reappeared (although of smaller magnitude) even though the land is now mostly covered with vegetation.

Whatever the explanation is, this is all going in the direction I have predicted (and wished) it will go.

So I don't believe this is temporary (although some phenomena may be cyclic, at least at first) and I see this as the announcement of future creation of small swamps outside of the forest and flooding of the area below, which should also include the creation of that spring I wished for.

24.3.13 2022.05.29

The ruptures are definitely back. I think there's even more of them than the first time I've noticed them, magnitudes and ground bumpiness are similar.

However, this time, dryness of the soil as the cause can definitely be ruled out. Not only have ruptures appeared in soil covered with grass and moss - they have appeared within 48 hours of very cloudy, moist and rainy weather.

There was no noticeable seismic activity in the area. All this is further strengthening the hypothesis that ruptures are created with pulses of underground fluid pressure.

A couple of months ago I have started planting some trees north (small patch of forest already exists south) and, more recently, vegetables on the land. I'm working in symbiosis with my god (Earth). This god is real, alive and doesn't need nor want prayers but is effectively responding to needs and wishes of neutral people (and neutral animals in general). When this land was ruled [by polarized people], it was left disturbed, relatively dry, barren and, in places, *infected* with plastic. After my transformation, I did not want to rule, I wished for this land to become fertile. I wished for healthy soil, I wished for the forest, fruits, vegetables. I wished for water, hot and cold, and I wished I do not have to water the plants myself. I wished a lot, but I didn't just wait or pray for it all to happen. I've

started enriching the soil, removing garbage and planting myself. God reacted quickly. Before the rain, he opens his land (creating ruptures) to soak in the water and store it in shallow aquifers for the trees.

I also wished for diversity. I've planted some plants myself, but soon discovered a lot of new different species on the land. After clearing some bush I discovered even fruits, which were obviously *planted* before I wished for them - indicating there's no strong causality here (but there's strong determinism and synchronicity).

I wished for wild onions, then I discovered chives (*Allium schoenoprasum*) - lots of it. I wished for it to grow next to vegetables I've planted, so I transplant a few of them there. Tomorrow, I notice some were already growing there.

I wish for good meat replacement, so I plant some beans. Soon, I discover wild legumes growing (e.g., *Vicia sativa*). *Robinia pseudoacacia* (black locust) was there from the start.

It feels so easy and natural, working with this god.

I'm not disturbing the soil when planting vegetables, I didn't even dig holes for all the seeds (I have only mulched the soil), I'm not removing *weeds*.

Wild animals frequently visit and trample higher vegetation (but not young tree seedlings) next to trees, mulching the soil - further helping to conserve water for plants, enrich the soil and grow the forest.

They did such a good job that one can now walk between trees like in a real forest (note that I explicitly wished for that too).

Small patch of precursor forest existed even before I wished for it, but it was just a small bunch of trees, black locusts mainly - it didn't have forest ground, it was lacking diversity and suffering.

I'm not watering anything myself, there was a longer period of dry sunny weather but [at least some] vegetables survived (the seeds have been planted one month ago). It is not summer yet though and there will probably be hotter periods - but I just don't feel like I will be doing the watering. I'm busy doing other chores on the land anyway.

People are generally selfish - they plant vegetables and don't share them with the wild, they don't even think about planting a forest. I planted trees first, and not for me - I plan to use some wood to insulate the house but I do not plan to use much wood, if any, for heating. I'd rather tremble in coldest cold than to destroy that patch of forest. God loves forests. I do too.

I've probably been happy at moments before, at least I feel I should've been, but happiness was always a word too strong to describe my feelings most of my life. But now, retreating from human slavery into the fellowship of god (or, fellowship of good), I see glimpses of hope.

In the midst of hell, we're growing good, we're recreating heaven. For, once in hell, one needs to create heaven to deserve heaven.

24.3.14 2022.05.31

One other thing I wished for was to have common vegetables growing as wild perennials (surviving winter and seeding naturally).

This can be achieved either with climate change or hybridization of vegetables with wild plants.

I still like snow and the experience of cold weather so this will probably be achieved with a combination of climate change and hybridization.

There are already candidates on the land - wild legumes and wild strawberries, for example.

I'd like for black locust (or perhaps oak) to hybridize with beans. This can generally hardly happen, so this will be achieved, as I hypothesized before, through horizontal gene transfer by viruses and/or bacteria.

Basically, in case of existing wild species, what I wish here is for wild plants to increase the size of fruits, but this also requires strengthening and increased size of the whole plant.

This could be achievable by human practice of cross-breeding and selection of suitable plants over generations, but with human interference, wild plants tend to lose their toughness and resistance. Reason for that is, of course, selfishness. With modest desires, minimal interference and patience, solutions good for everyone will emerge.

I don't want extra large fruits and vegetables like those that can be found in human markets, I would be satisfied with modest increase in size as long as the plant remains tough and fruits don't lose nutrients.

I'm already helping all this to happen. I have planted some tough resistant species of vegetables, but I am also doing experiments, trying to stimulate hybridization with minimal or absent physical interference.

UPDATE: Interestingly, just a couple of hours after I wrote this, while I was doing some chores on the land, I encounter the biggest wild strawberry I ever seen in my life.

Looking from distance, I thought it was an ordinary strawberry - as I have been throwing some seeds around (although not at this location), but it was a wild strawberry.

There were also more large ones beside that one. The plants on which they grow also have noticeably larger leaves. This is a good sign[45].

Perhaps just a bit larger size would be perfect, but even if this becomes the average size of wild strawberries here, I will be satisfied.

2024.05.15

This year, wild strawberries on average seem to be about 1.5 cm in

diameter. And this is not limited to those in the shade (where larger size may be expected).

24.3.15 2022.06.06

Increase in size is not limited to wild strawberries. *Urtica (kopriwa)*, for example, has grown in size considerably, as well as leaves on some oaks (as reported previously - in *Accelerated Evolution* chapter).

But what I find most interesting, is something I just discovered - young black locust trees with giant leaflets (leaves).

Leaflets on black locust are usually 2.5 - 5.1 cm long and 0.65 - 1.9 cm wide. On these new plants, however, they average 3-4 (!) times that size. Largest leaflets are 17 cm long and 8 cm wide.

I've noticed them a couple of days ago actually, next to older black locust trees, but, due to such extreme size, I assumed these were something else. Closer inspection today, however, revealed big spikes and other typical features of a black locust.

Interestingly, there are now other young plants with similarly sized leaves (leaflets) and structure, but with no spikes. I assume these are walnuts (something I have also recently wished for).

It is amazing how fast this land is transforming.

Note that I did not do any changes to the soil where these trees are growing. The area where I did some changes was the area further north - where I'm generally planting vegetables. This mainly includes mulching with hay/straw and spreading of organic waste, also some wooden ash. Apart from occasional urination, I wasn't using any fertilizers anywhere. I have been, however, removing some of blackberry (*kupina*) bushes to make room for the forest to grow.

Although I have hypothesized these changes will eventually become genetic, I don't think this is happening here just yet.

So what is the cause of this gigantism in local flora?

The main suspect might be [sudden increase in] nitrogen, however nitrogen alone is not enough. Everything associated with nitrogen fixation (e.g., bacteria) should also be on the increase.

Other key elements required are [increase in] water and adequate temperature. Neither have changed significantly in local atmosphere recently, implying that changes are underground.

Increased water availability should be stimulating the growth of nitrogen fixing microbes and ectomycorrhizal fungi. These fungi enable certain trees (e.g., oaks) to absorb CO₂ faster and, therefore, grow faster[46]. They are also slowing down the process of decay (rotting), thus, slowing down the release of carbon dioxide into atmosphere.

Symbiosis of trees with microbes and fungi is not only interesting as it is, this is exactly the type of symbiosis one would expect to *fossilize* into genes of a new organism - strong symbiosis in an environment stimulating such symbiosis.

Thus, I predict that trees will incorporate these micro-organisms into their genetics to enable a robust and efficient response to increasing CO₂.

The transfer will most likely be mediated by viruses (and possibly other microbes) - note that moisture is also helping here.

So this should be another evidence that recent seismic activity has influenced the local water-table, as hypothesized.

Gigantism has been noted before in places where Earth's crust has cracked[47]. In fact, one purpose of predicted increase in global earthquakes, is likely to ensure this supply of water and metals to plants and stimulate gigantism - as a reaction to CO₂ enriched climate, unsurprising for a self-regulating system.

However, response to changed climate is unlikely to be limited to one regulating effect. After all, area available for wild plants is decreasing, while emissions are still rising.

Therefore, the solution is likely to have different effects - depending on regions. I believe it will be beneficial only to human life in well-drained mountainous regions (neutral people seem to prefer mountains over plains and this is one of the reasons why, even if they're not conscious of it), while in plain areas, this will result in flooding - consequently limiting further emissions of greenhouse gases. Large lakes are carbon neutral. Oceans are carbon sinks. Lakes and oceans replacing human infrastructure would significantly affect human emissions. Thus, by this hypothesis, both should be increasing in area.

By my hypotheses, these floods are also not centuries away, first such floods are likely not even decades away.

Note that water flooding the plains won't only be undrinkable, it will be toxic - mainly due to diseases, pesticides and chemicals used and distributed by polarized people. So this is also a typical karmic reaction. Poison the land and you shall be poisoned.

But, like everything in nature, these floods have many different purposes. Like increased moisture in case of symbiosis of trees and microbes, floods here will enable horizontal gene transfer.

In this case, between polarized humans and domestic animals (i.e., dogs), transforming them into homo.gamma (chimeras).

Transformation of polarized humans into homo.gamma will make them more guidable but also less intelligent and less able to destabilize climate and environment again.

At that moment, polarized man will realize it does not rule this planet, it was only allowed the illusion that he is and will remain unregulated.

It might think, at first, that man created all these viruses, but very soon it'll realize that, even if man did, it was expected of him to do so by something bigger than even his ego. Then, it will be overwhelmed by feelings, but, as any dog, may have trouble expressing them. His expression of lying tears and fake care was a precursor of no tears and no care.

At that point, Earth, I reckon, will be a purgatory. A time where such creature will make a choice that was somewhere already made - whether it will continue regression or progression, genuine, this time.

24.3.16 2022.07.07

As I have mentioned before, when I first started adapting this land for myself and wild-life in general, prevailing plants were thorny bushes and thorny trees.

While I do like the fact that blackberry plants and locust trees grow here I wished for trees to prevail and I wished there would be no thorns on the plants.

And today I have discovered something remarkable - adult blackberry plants with large fruit but no prickles. I am aware that thornless blackberry cultivars have been bred by humans but I have never seem them in the wild and it is highly unlikely that humans had anything to do with these here. These were not planted here by anyone, the thornless ones are growing among other blackberry plants that still do have thorns. The fruit tastes similarly to a common wild blackberry (although it is 2-3 times bigger than wild blackberry fruit here).

All of this suggests this is a local genetic mutation. And it is likely not the only one.

Later, however, I realized that thorns are probably correlated with other properties of the plant so, in case of negative impact, I do not want the thorns to go away.

As mentioned before, there are young oaks with leaves that are much different than those in local oak species, and I have recently noticed that black locust leaves are changing too.

Also mentioned before was the fast growth and extreme size of some species

and their leaves. I haven't attributed these to genetic changes but now I'm not so sure anymore.

I have also recently noticed some odd behaviour in animals and there are signs that local people are changing too.

There are so many transformations on one small place in space and time that orthodox theories would struggle to explain this.

Of course, in case of blackberries, the effect could be explained by cross-pollination between different varieties - it cannot be excluded that some neighbour is growing a thornless variety nearby although I haven't noticed them anywhere. But this can't explain other changes.

One possibility could be the increased radiation that is causing or at least has a role in all these mutations (note that I have recently also detected increase in bit-flip events on my computer which should be caused by high-energy particles or radiation). I have been experiencing occasional expanding flashes of white light too (like supernovas) which seem to be the same as those experienced by astronauts outside of Earth's magnetosphere (Cosmic ray visual phenomena, or Astronaut's Eye). I have generally experienced these flashes with eyelids closed and while lying down before sleep but they have occurred during the day too.

But is the source cosmic, why here, why is it correlated with me and why are mutations correlated with my wishes (rather than being random)?

My theories actually can provide answers to all these questions.

Cosmic rays or cosmic radiation would imply some small magnetic anomaly (greatly decreased Earth's magnetic field strength in this case) exists above this place.

Online sources show no noticeable anomaly here but it is possible that instruments used have insufficient resolution to detect them. It is also possible that such anomalies are not permanent rather pop in and out of existence, escaping detection by orbiting satellites. However, with no global fragmentation of the magnetic dipole it would be hard to explain them.

The experience of white light flashes coupled with electronic incidents indeed suggests that anomalies are not constantly present - e.g., flashes of white light are not experienced continuously rather grouped into smaller periods (on the order of minutes) separated by longer intervals of inactivity (up to a day or more).

One explanation are occasional bursts of cosmic rays or radiation, strongly focused, probably at some point in Earth's magnetosphere or within the atmosphere.

Otherwise, energy would have to be coming from below ground.

Highly energetic particles and ionizing radiation are, however, generally associated with disease (e.g., cancer), so why they don't cause disease here (one could interpret the changes in plants here as diseases too, but

that seems very inappropriate)?

Well, as with every *poison*, it's all about the dosage. Studies have shown that low doses of ionizing radiation are stimulating and/or beneficial rather than harmful[48].

And that certainly seems to be the case here - exposure to ionizing radiation is not continuous rather occasional (pulsed). As such it stimulates growth and provides other benefits. It might even keep some people here safe[49] from cancer[50].

In example, my father had operated cancer years ago (before the radiation increase), but he recovered and cancer never came back - perhaps this radiation is keeping it at bay.

It makes sense - if one trains the immune system with a low dose of a virus one is making the system much stronger against that virus. Similarly, low dose of ionizing radiation translates to a low dose of cancer causing free radicals. It would not be surprising then that this makes the organism effectively immune to cancer.

Note however, that, despite the abundant evidence, western medicine is refusing to accept the fact that low doses of ionizing radiation are beneficial - the reason is probably the fact that it prefers to treat (not cure) diseases in people (in case of cancer, with big doses of ionizing radiation!) rather than prevent them from appearing in the first place.

However, I do not believe all changes here are caused by radiation directly (radiation induced mutations in genes are generally point-like and cause errors in function rather than providing new function). Radiation might simply act as a trigger enabling horizontal gene transfer between different species.

In any case, everything suggests there's highly energetic radiation here and there's accelerated genetic transformation, forming a localized space-time moment of predicted strong evolution, or a precursor to such evolution on global scale.

But how big is the affected place?

So far, I can confirm the effect on *my* land and the land my parents claim below to the east (area of some 12000 m², or 1.2 hectares). No one else in the neighbourhood has reported anything similar so this might, at least at this point, be limited to the place where I live.

This ain't a coincidence. I have stopped being cancer for god [Earth] and now the god is keeping me safe from cancer (see note above). I don't poison his land, I keep it healthy and diverse, and he's stimulating growth and beneficial hybridization. We all benefit.

But, as stated already, this is a precursor to global radiation - will that radiation be beneficial or dosed poisonous? Will it keep humans safe from diseases or will it be used to kill the cancer that is human?

I already know the answer - cure through transformation and death. Yet, I

reckon that those who follow my work with theirs and those whose work I follow will survive the apocalypse that is upon us without dying from human form.

However, I still don't see followers of that work here, I see followers of form everywhere, a form that stimulates addiction to degradation of soul, not work that stimulates the growth of soul.

24.3.17 2022.11.02

Recently started noticing dandelion with giant leaves (about 30 cm) and stems up to incredible 50-60 cm in length. I have also seen signs that this gigantism might be spreading to neighbouring lands.

There are also more signs of transformation of the land into forest floor - mushrooms. Previously, I've been finding only meadow mushrooms (e.g., puffballs and *Agaricus*) here. Later I've been finding false truffles (*Scleroderma citrinum* species) and edible *Xerocomus*. And yesterday I've found *Macrolepiota*. These are mushrooms typically growing in forests or forest edges.

Interestingly, I was searching for *Macrolepiota* in the nearby forest the day before yesterday (on 2022.10.31), but I didn't find it (last time I searched and found these mushrooms was at least 1 year ago, probably more) and then the next day (2022.11.01) I encounter it on *my* land. Another nice synchronicity and confirmation that the local god is effectively responding to my wishes.

Of course, I didn't pick this mushroom, I've left it to spread its spores and multiply. It will take some time before I can live off this land, but I believe these initial signs are announcements of abundant local future and increasing local diversity, as long as I continue living in symbiosis with god.

2023.10.31

Nice synchronicity, today, exactly one year after I encountered the *Macrolepiota* mushroom, I encountered 3 *Macrolepiota* mushrooms in the same place. This time I harvested some, 1.5 of them. I've also encountered several different species of fungi I wasn't seeing here before. All seem to be edible. Great.

2023.11.16

Three more nice *Macrolepiota* mushrooms, in the same place. Not sure if this kind of information is relevant, but I feel the need to log these mushroom encounters, it may turn out to be useful. Repetition of the number 3 is interesting.

Over the years, I have been occasionally finding giant *Agaricus* on nearby land, however, this year (about 1-2 months ago) the amount and size of these giants exceeded anything I've seen before.

One particular mushroom had a stem about 40 cm long and about 9 cm thick on average, with a hat \approx 30 cm in diameter. These mushrooms are starting to

look like small trees.

25 Asteroids and comets

I have predicted larger asteroids/comets will be impacting Earth in near future. I have also predicted that these will have precursors in the form of [increasing frequency of] smaller meteors (fireballs), meteorites and micro-meteorites and that some of these will, as precursors, land near (or, as I wished, on) my [precursor] house.

Well, apparently, this is happening. There are reports of increased frequency of meteors, or at least sightings of meteors (whether this is a real increase is another question). But that's not all. Two days before I wrote this chapter, on 2022.12.14, the rocks (along with unusually shaped ice) have suddenly appeared on my house. These are, however, probably not meteorites, but they do seem as perfect precursors to meteorites that I have predicted will fall here. The full story and detailed analysis is available in my B.Log[51].

26 Fellowship with god

People destined for transformation already are and will continue transforming to neutral [sub]species. This transformation is also a transition from the support of unsustainable industries and cancerous systems towards the symbiosis with god. My symbiosis with god started about the year 2017. At first it was subtle but it has been increasing ever since.

I have already written in some chapters above how god is helping me and how I'm helping god but I realized this should continue in a chapter of its own. So here's more of the story.

26.1 Tamed blackberries (2023.02.10)

I've mentioned previously how I was clearing some blackberry bushes in order to make room for the forest. At first, I thought I need to clear that bush thoroughly - not only cut down the shoots but also dig out the roots. So that's what I started doing. However, as I was digging out the roots every now and then I would hurt some animal, typically an earthworm but sometimes even a blindworm.

This was very dissatisfying for me, I didn't like disturbing the soil and I simply couldn't continue the practice. So I stopped taking out the roots and accepted the, usually very likely, possibility that I will have to repeat the cutting every now and then in order to get rid of the bush. But god obviously knew what I was doing and why I was doing it because I've soon witnessed a miracle.

New shoots of blackberry did start growing again but they were quickly outrun by thick grass and one interesting species of vine (not of the grape family). The vines strongly twined around the blackberry shoots keeping them

tied to the ground, while the thick grass prevented sunlight from reaching the shoots.

I realized this is the optimal solution - since the shoots are grounded and shadowed they won't stop the trees from growing and they won't prevent me from walking between the trees, I can simply walk over the thin shoots. Not only that, this thick natural mulch will help retain moisture and nutrients so trees will grow stronger and faster. And perhaps some blackberry fruit will still grow from these grounded shoots and I can pick them up like I would pick strawberries.

This guy is a genius.

26.2 Increasing edibility (2023.02.27)

I figured that most plants growing here are not very toxic, but generally not very edible either. Most of the perennial plants have sour taste. So I wished for food to be more edible here.

I started planting vegetables but every now and then I would notice some new perennials growing here as well. I notice one interesting new plant that initially looked like young spinach. It seemed like it could be edible so I try chewing a bit and, to my amazement, it tasted very edible - a nice mild taste, not sour at all. Soon, I've discovered many more edible and useful species.

If one needs safety.. It is generally not safe to swallow even small bits of poisonous plants (or mushrooms). General test for edibility is such:

1. separate the plant into its components: roots, leaves, seeds/flowers, fruit and stem,
2. rub each part on your wrist or arm and wait a few minutes, if skin tingles, goes numb, itches, or develops a rash, discard the plant,
3. if possible, cook the plants (some plants are not edible raw but are when boiled or cooked),
4. hold each part to your lips for a few minutes then wait ≈ 15 minutes and discard if there's any sort of reaction,
5. take a small bite, chew, and discard if the flavour is extremely bitter or soapy,
6. swallow the small bite and wait about 8 hours before trying more and waiting another 8 hours, if there's still no reaction, it's likely safe.

Notes for those who do not need as much safety:

- not all parts of the plant will be poisonous (or equally poisonous) so there shouldn't be any need to test all parts for edibility if one does not intend to use all of them,

- low toxicity is often beneficial rather than harmful,
- most toxins can be degraded by boiling but sometimes the procedure can be more complicated (although that often means boiling multiple times) and sometimes it may not be worth it,

When I see something *looking edible*, my procedure is to take a small bite, chew it for a few seconds and spit it all out regardless of taste, if taste is good and I don't get sick I repeat it tomorrow with a bit more, swallowing the content this time, if I don't get sick by the next day I consider that part of the plant edible. Sometimes I even skip the first step but then again I'm in good relations with my god (which doesn't make it absolutely safe though).

If I see something *looking poisonous* I do some research on it to confirm it. Note that positive identification generally requires exhaustive research (two species can be very similar and yet one can be edible while the other is deadly and some sources won't mention the poisonous lookalike at all) and even I'm usually not skipping it, especially when it comes to mushrooms (although nowadays I mostly do exhaustive research out of curiosity rather than fear).

Also, looks can be deceiving and generally say nothing about toxicity, "looking edible" and "looking poisonous" is something I can use after substantial experience, research, symbiosis with, and guidance by, the god, but even I cannot yet solely rely on intuition. Although, so far, it has been proven correct many times, it is not infallible and it would be delusional to claim otherwise. But it definitely is useful.

At times I was thinking of common spices and how I could obtain them locally. I wished for plants to provide at least some. Soon I've found a plant with a very piquant taste (peppery/cabbage like) that can serve as a very good alternative to common pepper. I've also identified a plant that can provide mustard. I can get sugar from fruit but I've also found trees growing here from which a sugary sap can be extracted. Hot peppers I can grow myself. All I'm missing now is salt.

26.3 Fulfilling wishes (2023.05.04)

My experience has convinced me that the more neutral a person becomes the more its wishes materialize. My symbiosis with god is steadily increasing with my effective neutrality and my wishes are increasingly coming true. Here I'll mention some examples not mentioned elsewhere. As mentioned before, I have wished for increased edibility of plants growing here, but I did not mention I had some special *requests* too. Some of these are hazelnuts, walnuts and sweet chestnuts. Now, I have confirmed walnut and hazel trees have started growing here - I've found 3-4 young walnut (*Juglans regia*) trees and 1 hazel (*Corylus*

avellana) tree. The appearance of the hazel tree here is particularly interesting because I haven't seen hazel trees anywhere nearby.

The seeds of these trees have been, most likely, brought here by neutral (wild) animals, but the method is not so relevant to me, the effect is (although I do prefer wild animals bringing seeds here rather than polarized humans). A polarized human might interpret this synchronicity as coincidence, but even such creature cannot deny that my wishes are, effectively, coming true here.

All I'm missing now is the chestnut.

2024.08.29

I have planted some chestnut seeds some time after this was written. It seems that 2-3 (out of 9) could survive.

26.3.1 Sawdust (2024.12.14)

About a year ago, I've started doing some project for which I needed certain materials. Most of these materials I could slowly produce and accumulate on my own, and I did, but I was missing one ingredient - sawdust. Then, about a year after, my father, after more than 20 years, starts doing carpentry, working with wood again. I got my sawdust, a lot of it. This will be very useful, not just for the project I have in mind, but also to enrich the soil. Wishes can come true indeed, but time is needed when working with god, or good, that usually operates on different timescales, at least if one cares about long-term sustainability. How much time - depends on one's karma and the rate of evolution. Over the years, I've learned not to ask my self how much of something I can get and how much time something will take. One can equate this time as expectation or patience, but once the soul learns not to practice patience, renouncing expectations, patience is not needed at all, everything simply happens exactly when the time is right. Similarly, without caring about how much one will get of something, the amount will be right. 自然

26.4 Evil part of god (2023.03.18)

No one can be absolutely good. We're all made of relatively good and relatively bad parts. From my perspective, wild flora, fauna and wild habitats are good parts of god, while polarized people and their domestic animals are generally bad, even evil, parts of god (greater good). While all the good parts of god are commonly working in my interest and are indeed making my wishes come true, the evil parts of god tend to work against it (some sometimes, though, probably under subconscious influence, do help me). This, of course, I understand as karma, a consequence of my own polarized past.

In example, I do not like and I do not wish to be surrounded by polarized people and their polarized pets and this is one of the reasons I started building my house in the hills where I was supposed to be at least a bit away from civilization, enough not be bothered by constant presence of polarized animals.

But here my precursor nature becomes a problem (in fact, none of my predictions of future which are coming true, didn't bring me anything good from people so far). I should have known that if I run to the hills, others will soon be running too, in case of polarized people, not for the same reasons.

It doesn't make sense to move far away if one's past is following behind. At some point one will have to stop and endure the karmic reaction. This is one of the reasons I did not run far away even though I initially wanted to.

And this is happening. My father goes up there every day (at least when the weather permits), as well as people in neighbouring lands. Not only that, my father now says he will build a house there (right above mine) and move there because he will be forced out of his current house eventually (due to debt of course).

And just to the right of my house, a neighbour has already started building a small dwelling and already expressed a will to move there from the city where he usually lives.

Then there are dogs coming up with all these people and some of them are barking at me even though they are on, what would polarized people call, my property. But this is happening even downhill below at my parents' house. The dogs are going crazy, their owners probably will too although they are crazy already, from my perspective.

So I'm trying to work on *my* property when there's no one around and I'm not forced to interact with them, but that ain't easy.

Of course, I could just ignore the polarized when I encounter them but I'm not sure on that. If one doesn't interact with them and noticeably avoids them they will call one crazy and eventually that becomes an

excuse for them to do more harm to one.

UPDATE 2023.05.04:

I'm tired of working against my self so I have started ignoring some people (animals) completely. Feeling much better.

On top of that, I'm constantly having trouble with tools, they're old and constantly breaking up. I'm just tired of everything, but I know I will endure, as long as there's some good of god near me. However, while I'm trying to preserve it, covering concrete with nature and letting trees grow, these people are, still, doing the opposite. In occasional pulses of polarized thoughts, I wonder will they transform or will they remain liars and thieves who will, eventually, once they lose what they treasure, stop treating *my* treasure as such and just take whatever good I left growing on it. But I am not angry at them, nor I will be angry if that happens, I'm really not pleased with my self having such thoughts.

*White man came across the sea
He brought us pain and misery
He killed our tribes, he killed our creed
He took our game for his own need ...
Run to the hills
Run for your lives*

Run to the hills, Iron Maiden

26.5 Growing food (2024.08.29)

For the past 3-4 years I'm experimenting with cultivation of edible plants. I'm not crazy about gardening but, at this point, I don't see any other choice if one does not want to support the evil system. My goal is to be able to survive entire year on my own produce. And, with barren land and no usage of money, that ain't easy. Sure, at times it seems that god is helping me, but most of the time I still feel human past and present dragging me down. The soil is mostly heavy compacted clay (a consequence of human abuse of the land) and, while I know how to fix that, it will take years to make enough land usable for cultivation of a larger amount of food. But much bigger obstacle is the climate and water. There's no food without water and there's no water here. I've dug up a bigger area of land to capture rainwater during winter, which helped last year when there was enough rain, but this year is disastrous. My lake has dried up weeks or months ago. In the last 2 months, except on 1 occasion, there have been no noticeable rain, and even on that one occasion, it was only 20 mm. So, this year, I've dug up additional area for another lake, which will hopefully be filled over autumn and winter but it is unlikely to be enough. As for this year vegetables, I had to haul water from the house down the hill every day to water the plants. This was mostly limited to 7 litres per day because that

water resource is limited as well - it is used in the house by the family. And it's not easy to haul water over 300 metres uphill. And what can one do with 7 litres? That's enough to water 1-2 plants properly here, so naturally I had to give up on a lot of plants. The temperatures during these last two months - steadily over 33 °C, commonly reaching much more, up to 39 °C. And there's no rain in weather reports for the next 10 days either (of course, these things are unreliable, but I've noticed that any prediction of rain this year usually turns out to be wrong, so no rain in the next 10 days is not at all unlikely). Even the trees are drying up. There are a lot of oaks full of brown leaves already. They might survive this, but they're obviously suffering a lot. On top of that, it seems every year there's got to be one extreme storm. Last year in July a storm with unprecedented winds for this location (120 km/h), this year in July hail of the size of tennis balls. This season is pretty much over for me. So how much food did I get this year? Much less than last year even though I've planted much much more. One definitely cannot be optimistic about the future. In fact, it's hard not to be desperate and give up. But my subconscious doesn't want me to give up. There are certain little things that keep one going. One thing is that I believe I have found the optimal garden bed solution that could be long-term sustainable (as long as there's some water available and as long as temperatures don't become too extreme). The other thing is that *my* forest is expanding. These are mostly black locust trees, which seem to be very drought-resistant - so that's very good to have. Another thing is that I've finally seen a seedling of pawpaw emerging in the garden. Out of 10 seeds planted, to my knowledge only one has emerged so far, but lifts up the spirits. I've also planted chestnut seeds last year before winter and, while most didn't or probably won't survive, two seedlings are doing reasonably well. These things are great but, honestly, if it comes to that that I have to survive on the food I produce myself anytime soon, overall, things aren't looking good. And anytime later? Well, climate certainly won't be becoming better overall.. The way I see it, unless god shifts to a higher gear here, my goal will hardly be achieved before my current source of food dries up, or before I start to refuse it - because it is coming from the unsustainable and evil system. I am, in fact in a dilemma. What I am certain about is that I want to get what I deserve. But by taking food coming from the system I'm still supporting the devil, no matter how minimally. Do I deserve then for things to get better for my gardening, just because it should set me free from the system eventually? Or should I just stop taking that food right away and live as long as I manage to live on my own? Which, of course, unless a miracle happens, wouldn't last long. Well, 6 years ago I was convinced I have to stop everything that has anything to do with the system, including eating, but my subconscious prevented me from departure. Was it the right decision? Being a true believer in reincarnation, I'm not afraid of death, but I hate risk of doing something which will eventually cause suffering. And I've learned a lot in these 6 years. I believe the minimal support for the devil shouldn't be a problem if it's compensated with equal support for god. And by increasing efforts to grow my own food, fertilizing the land with waste, increasing diversity and helping to preserve the land from the devil I am increasingly supporting

the god while decreasing my support for the devil. Ultimately, the question is, if I die will the things for god and this god's land be better or worse? Again, I believe I'm doing something good for the land here and I don't want to risk for the things to get worse. But what if god is asking the same question, and the things would be better for his world and him if he dies? Well, that's something I do not know, and with my limitations possibly cannot know (but want to know!). So what am I then supposed to do? Well, I guess the best I can do is to act on what do I know for certain or reasonably certain and continue learning, about god and the world. That's it.

27 Disintegration and decay

I have mentioned previously how my tools are breaking often. Not only that, it seems to me they're disintegrating faster (e.g., due to faster rusting). I have hypothesized previously that during accelerated evolution decay rates of elements are temporarily increased (proportionally to the rate of evolution). This implies an effect on molecular forces as well. Prior to disintegration of tools I have already noticed how my clothes and sheets are disintegrating fast. I have noticed this mostly on clothes and sheets in use, so some wear is expected, but I find it happening at an unusually high rate and magnitude. I've noticed that one of my t-shirts even became transparent.

Of course, this increase in wear here may not be caused by changes in molecular forces at this point (or, not dominantly at least) but I do see this as a precursor of increase in disintegration/decay rates globally, which at some point will be.

27.1 2023.11.08

For quite some time I'm noticing increased amounts of lost head/beard hair, mostly in and around food. Now, others in the house have started reporting the same thing too (including my sister who lives here now with her children). I don't think this is part of normal process of ageing, rather an anomaly or consequence of accelerated evolution. Apart from that, I'm experiencing increased amounts of vertigo. I have been experiencing episodes of this before (I've used to correlate it with increase in smoking) so this is probably benign but the *episode* is now lasting longer (probably over a week now) and is more severe (affecting my daily life).

The vertigo is, of course, not present all the time. I feel it mostly when leaning my head backwards and while getting up, but also during position changes while in bed. However, although there is no vertigo in between, there exists a mild feeling of nausea and headache.

I wonder, are the two phenomena correlated with [increase in frequency and strength of] radiation on the locality, the possible symptoms of which I've already noticed (e.g., bitflip events, bright flashes in eyes). Or is this another manifestation of weakening of molecular forces. Possibly both.

In any case, all this is predicted with strong evolution, the fact which, however, doesn't really make the situation much more pleasant.

Interestingly, relatively synchronized with the experience of vertigo (perhaps with its maximum), there was a big solar storm on 2023.11.05, which even induced a visible Aurora here[52], something very rare on this latitude (or at least, it used to be rare, it should become less rare by the predictions).

27.2 2023.12.31: Smelling decay

Another phenomenon that surely does have the potential to represent a precursor to a global one. I have been recently exposed to increased levels of hydrogen sulphide (H_2S) gas in the house. It took months before I finally identified the culprit and solved the problem. At the same time I have been reading about past major mass extinctions. Hydrogen sulphide is usually produced by sulfate-reducing bacteria living in anoxic conditions (e.g., in sewers, depths of the Black Sea) and is considered to have played a role at least in some mass extinctions (notably in Permian-Triassic) where it is also correlated with the depletion of the stratospheric ozone. This and my relatively long unpleasant exposure to this highly toxic gas suggests to me this should be interpreted as another precursor.

This exposure has likely contributed to daily experienced vertigo and headaches noted previously. The vertigo was subdued roughly at the same time as the exposure to the gas stopped.

The source of exposure, of course, will be probably different globally. For me it was the broken indoor sewer pipe (it took me so long to fix the problem because I assumed the smell was coming from outside - as it did occasionally come before, due to a full septic tank). Globally, one reason could be anoxic waters, but no one is expecting this. More likely, probably, are regular sudden expulsions of accumulated hydrogen sulphide (it is known to come up with methane) from underground reservoirs, e.g., from melting Arctic permafrost (although, we might be talking about locked-in deep sea deposits here as well). Increasingly meandering polar jet stream could then bring hydrogen sulphide to mid-latitudes. Some could interpret it as Earth's flatulence. Which does seem appropriate. By my theory of planetary neurogenesis, the south pole could be

interpreted as Earth's mouth (currently closed). It makes sense then that the antipodal point (north pole) is the anus equivalent.

I'm convinced that at least some species of life on Earth will be guided towards the south pole. Some could be guided by magnetic fields, but regardless of mechanism, it is the increasing habitability of Antarctica coupled with decreasing habitability elsewhere which will be luring and concentrating animals (people included) south. Eventually, the ground will open and most of these will be effectively swallowed and transferred deeper inside Earth (perhaps as large carbon or DNA fragments, if not as living individuals). There are multiple interpretations of this. One interpretation is similar to the incorporation of mitochondria into standard living cells (with Earth here representing a relative cell equivalent). Other interpretation is a planetary neurogenesis event where life is transferred into layers of the upper mantle (representing equivalents of brain layers). Third interpretation is simply feeding.

Note that neurogenesis events are equivalent to mitochondria-acquisition - precursor neural cells and/or proteins are cultivated on epidermis, then *swallowed* and transferred to brain layers. If this involves death/transformation of precursors then it is equivalent to feeding as well.

This kind of transfer happens during major mass extinction events (at least), so Earth' upper mantle layers should already contain life (which, I argue in my theories, can also be living life, as the theory predicts and provides mechanisms for habitable zones). Build-up of gases in the depths of the north pole may include fossil gases sourced in this life, rather than surface life. Thus, the amounts of fossil fuels and hydrogen sulphide in the Arctic could be severely underestimated.

2024.10.30

For maybe a month now I am experiencing vertigo again. I occasionally sense H₂S, most likely coming from the sewer outside the house, but I am not sure if that's the culprit even it likely was the last time, unless I am sensitive even to smaller concentrations that may be present constantly but my nose/brain cannot detect. But it is interesting that this is happening at the same time of the year as the last time. Atmospheric pressure is higher at this time of the year which makes it more likely that H₂S will enter the house. The location of the sewer is very unfortunate for me. The house is on a hill and the sewer is just south/south-east of the house. Since the atmospheric pressure is somewhat lower on the back of the house, wind drafts through the

house tend to flow from the south to the north, carrying the shit with it. It doesn't help that I like to keep my windows open during the day, even in colder weather.

27.3 2024.07.19: Bubbling

I have two water reservoirs on the land. Last one was created recently (few months ago) and is about 2 metres deep. The other one was created a couple of years ago and is deeper and bigger. That one is like a small lake or pond, filled with rainwater. The lake is partially covered with a roof built with logs, branches and straw. Now, I'm observing something very interesting happening in that lake. For the last couple of days, bubbles have been present on the surface. Today, in the interval of 10-15 minutes, I have observed sporadic bubbling on about 10 different places in the lake. The gas is seeping from the ground. The water level has dropped by 15-20 cm in the last 1-2 days, which cannot be explained by evaporation alone. I'm using water from this lake to water the plants occasionally so the gradual decrease in water level is expected but not a sudden one. And I haven't used any significant amount of water for watering in the last 1-2 days. Due to relatively large depth, the roof cover (keeping the deepest part of the lake in good shade) and significant capacity for rainwater capture, water is present in the lake year-round. Water is mainly stagnant, muddy, and relatively rich in nutrients, with patches of denser mats of organic material on the surface (e.g., bacteria). There is no vegetation growing in the pond but intermittent supply of organic material is present through runoff during rains and infall from the roof structure. Anoxic conditions are likely present in the deeper parts of the pond.

Therefore, microbial production of methane probably occurs in the sediment. The methane is probably accumulating dissolved in sediment porewaters during high water levels. As the water level drops, and combined partial pressures of the dissolved gases exceed the hydrostatic pressure, bubbles are formed[53]. Those that grow large enough for their buoyancy to overcome the combined hydrostatic pressure and cohesive strength of the sediment, migrate upward to the surface. Sudden drop in water level may be explained by sudden release of larger amount of accumulated gas, although I'm not sure how plausible such explanation is here, as it requires a very large gas accumulation compared to pond size.

With global warming and increasing exploitation, water levels in lakes are decreasing globally. This then could be interpreted as a precursor to a global increase in methane emissions from lakes. Of course, relativity in such interpretation is relatively high, as this has been already happening for years in some parts of the world (e.g., Arctic) before I observed it happening here. If one, instead, interprets this as a precursor to increase in methane emissions from larger lakes concentrated about this latitude (45°) or about the equatorial re-

gions, precursor interpretation is less relative. However, intermittent methane emissions are already present in these regions, at least in managed water reservoirs (e.g., Harsha lake, US[54]). One could also interpret this as a precursor to sudden sharp drops in water levels globally (correlated with seismic activity?). Whatever the interpretation, I believe we will be witnessing larger bursts of methane emissions spreading and increasing globally.

Interestingly, a couple of hours later I encounter news that lake Rusanda in Serbia dried completely[55] for the first time[56]. This lake is 190 km away and basically on the same latitude (the difference is only 33 km). According to EMSC, there were a couple of earthquakes on this latitude relatively near. A 4.1 magnitude one near Ukraine-Romania border on 2024.07.12 and a 1.5 magnitude one near Zagreb on 2024.07.13 (some 170 km away from my location). If one connects the two locations with a straight line in Google Maps, lake Rusanda is less than 10 km away from the line (about 30 km from the measurement line in Google Earth), however, any deeper correlation between these 3 events seems unlikely. Can the sharp drop in water level in Rusanda be solely explained by the heat wave? The lake Rusanda is (was?) extremely salty and it is the saltiest lake in Serbia. Salt can somewhat reduce evaporation rates, but the lake is also not very big (about 4 km²), it is shallow, 1.5 m in depth (probably equal to the current water level in my lake, which is at least 2.5 m when full). However, the lake has fluvial origin and has (or had?) salt-water springs on the bottom[57]. Similarly to my lake, the water in Rusanda (when present) is muddy and yellow due to presence of humus. The lake has a layer of black mud, 1 m thick on average, thicker near springs. Without the mud layer, it appears that lake depth would be about 2.5 m, equal to the depth of my lake. Multiple synchronicity here. I find the presence of salt-water springs very interesting. Not only because I have wished for springs to appear on my location but also because I wished for Pannonian sea to be restored here, at least to some extent. Rusanda is located within the Pannonian basin as well. If freshwater reservoirs are drying up perhaps we'll see an increase in saltwater springs? I'd like to have both, thank you. :-)

2024.07.25

The bubbling is still present. Largest bubbles are about 1.5 - 2 cm in diameter. I'm not sure, however, that the gas here is methane. I have tried igniting the bubbles but there was no noticeable ignition. Either the gas is not flammable or the concentration of flammable

gases is low. If there's oxygen in the upper layers, dissolved methane rising from depths can be oxidized by bacteria, but methane rising from depth accumulated in bubbles should not be affected as much. However, research shows that anaerobic oxidation can occur even in anoxic conditions[58]. These, then, could be bubbles of CO₂.

2024.07.27

Today, I've tried poking the water with a stick. To my surprise, water layer was shallow. It appears that the last 1 m of the lake is completely filled with mud (so it's exactly of the same thickness as the mud layer in Rusanda lake). Disturbing the bed, of course, caused a lot of bubbling. I've excavated some of it (which wasn't easy!), it is a thick sticky black substance (should be usable in the garden when dried). While I did expect mud to accumulate in the lake, I certainly did not expect this much of it (it's probably not all black though). But I did predict accelerated evolution, 1 metre of sediment per year becoming normal?

2024.12.31

It's winter, but the bubbling still occurs. I didn't notice it in the covered part of the lake but I did notice bubbles trapped in ice in the shallow part (the covered part doesn't freeze). The ice seems to form over night and then melts during the day. I did not observe the melting, but the pattern of ridges in the ice and the bubbles are different every day. The slope differential is low here and the bubbles have been observed even right next to the shore. Organic content here is very low, much lower than in the deeper/covered part of the lake and I didn't observe the bubbles in another lake (which gets partially frozen as well). There are actually a lot of bubbles but most are small (≤ 1 mm), some are over 2 cm in diameter. Given the size and distribution of bubbles (smaller ones are closer to the shore), obviously the size is roughly proportional to pressure, so the source is probably the same and the production occurs in a shallow layer. The source are probably microbes (the ice could even help to increase their activity as it forms an insulating layer), but again, I see it as a precursor to something bigger. Note that bubbles can also form by the expulsion of dissolved gases from the water forming ice, but such bubbles are never spherical[59] and have a thickness on the μm scale (although can be elongated to larger sizes). While some smaller bubbles here could represent expelled dissolved gases, most of them are very spherical, and I have even observed bubbles rising from the bottom occasionally. What can be seen here may then be interpreted as the announcement of cyclic thawing of frozen lakes

on a larger scale and, thus, cyclic release of trapped greenhouse gases. Perhaps the cyclic thawing of Arctic/Antarctic ice is relatively imminent, with the complete melting occurring each polar day (the Polar polar day). That would probably be the most appropriate interpretation of this precursor.

Since the bubbling is present only in the northern lake, I've started calling this one The North Pole, the other one The South Pole. Seems appropriate.

2025.06.01

The cyclic freezing of the lakes has stopped. Based on happenings here one could estimate that the global cycling of polar ice will last for about 10 years and then the ice will completely disappear, even during winter. But of course, one should be very sceptic about this estimate. It is clear, however, that the Earth currently is on a trajectory towards the complete loss of ice, and at least the complete loss of sea ice during summer is already *baked in* (bound to happen, regardless of future greenhouse gas emissions).

If one does interpret what's happening here as a precursor, one could also ask how to interpret the covered part of the lakes? The northern lake has a straight roof on the north side, made out of black locust branches and other vegetation. The southern lake has a similar roof but on the south side, and with the addition of polyurethane panels (leftovers from other construction projects) as the base. I've constructed these roofs in order to insulate the lakes (to decrease water loss through evaporation). Perhaps humans will build bigger similar structures on north and south poles, albeit with a different intention (or the same - once the ice is gone completely). In fact, I consider that very likely (and probably the same materials will be used), as I have already predicted elsewhere that life will move towards the poles with time, and settle on the south pole eventually.

28 The end

It ain't easy being a general precursor during the extinction. In fact, it's miserable. On one hand, I really want to stop being one, on the other, I still want to experience some phenomena I have correlated with precursor nature, such as local meteorite(s) and water source(s). When does it end? Or, at least, when does the dominance of negative implications end? Well, things are increasingly being synchronized, difference in time between global phenomena and precursors has decreased significantly, even becoming negative in some cases. I believe

this indicates the turning (tipping?) point is near. I'm turning 43 tomorrow, half of my predicted age of death. Could the turning point be about now? I really wouldn't mind...

It is also halfway between my two major soul energy levels (transformation points), 36 y and 50 y.

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